

**FORSCHUNGSBERICHTE DES
INSTITUTS FÜR BETRIEBSWIRTSCHAFTSLEHRE
DER UNIVERSITÄT WIEN**

Supplementary Appendix to “Comments
and Refinements on the Pay as you wish
Model by Chen et al. (2017)”

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Lehrstuhl für Marketing
Juni 2020

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June 2020

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1 Introduction and setup

In Akbari and Wagner (2020) we discuss extensions of the Pay as you wish (PAYW) model by Chen et al. (2017) (CKZ hereafter). The setup of the mathematical derivations of the model leads to complicated and long expressions. Due to readability considerations and the page limit for the submission to *Marketing Science*, these derivations are omitted from the paper and the appendices of the paper. However, reproducibility concerns call for the disclosure of our calculation paths. Therefore, this report aims to support the reader of our work in retracing the results in the paper and the appendices. Accordingly, this report can be regarded as an ‘appendix to the appendices.’

In addition to disclosing our calculation paths, we also try to reconstruct the results of CKZ in this report. Although parts of these derivations have already been discussed in the original CKZ model, their derivations are not always accessible and sometimes flawed.

In Akbari and Wagner (2020) we run a simulation analysis to quantify the consequences of the misspecifications in CKZ. This article also presents the code and extended results on this simulation in Section 6.

1.1 Notation conventions

This report strives for consistent notation. However, the results discussed in this report are based on two different sources, Akbari and Wagner (2020) and CKZ. Hence, it is necessary to find notational compromises between consistency, compactness and comparability within this report.

Therefore, the following conventions are established in this report:

- Auxiliary variables are typically denoted in uppercase letters and numbered alphabetically. The letter C is usually omitted to avoid confusion with costs (c). This might lead to a different notation in the report than in the paper. In some cases, the original notation from the manuscript is retained. When deviating from these rules, we point to the difference in notation between the sources.
- The sequencing starts anew in each chapter (and, in some cases, subchapter). Subscripts indicate the respective (sub-)section. For compactness, subscripts of auxiliary variables are abbreviated for PAYW with a minimum price (PAYW-MP becomes MP) and PAYW with a suggested price (PAYW-SP becomes s).

- As profit functions play an important role in Chapter 5, their subscripts always include the entire name of the pricing policy instead of the abbreviation.
- Superscripts are used to indicate special conditions of parameters (e.g., $\beta = 0$) and to distinguish different versions by different authors.
- An asterisk (*) as a superscript denotes an optimal value. A plus (+) denotes a critical value.
- We drop the index for consumers, i , when we take the sellers perspective.
- CKZ sometimes use different notation conventions (e.g., they use asterisks to denote both, optimal values and critical values). In this case we align their notation with ours. This might lead to different labels. To avoid confusion, please confer to the list of abbreviations.
- When referring to equations in the main body of our manuscript, we will use the abbreviation AW followed by the respective number of the equation (e.g., (1) will become (AW.1)). When referring to equations of the appendices in our manuscript, we will use AW.A. and the respective number (e.g., (A.1) will become (AW.A.1)), and when referring to equations in CKZ, we add “CKZ” in front of the equation (e.g., (1) will become (CKZ.1)). These equations are not necessarily notationally equivalent, however, they have a similar meaning.

1.2 Fundamentals in CKZ’s PAYW model

In this section, we summarize the most important assumptions in CKZ’s model. In their paper, CKZ model consumer behavior based on two important equations, the consumer’s utility function and the perceived fair price.

The consumer’s utility function includes advantageous, disadvantageous inequity aversion, consumption utility, and the perceived fair price,

$$u_i = r_i - p_i - \beta_i \max\{p_i - r_{i0}, 0\} - \gamma_i \max\{r_{i0} - p_i, 0\}, \quad \beta_i, \gamma_i \geq 0. \quad (1)$$

(CKZ.1)

(AW.1)

This utility function originates from Fehr and Schmidt (1999). However, CKZ contribute to the literature by introducing the perceived fair price, which is given by

$$r_{i0} = \begin{cases} c & r_i \leq c \\ \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c & r_i > c \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

(AW.2)

Furthermore, CKZ make assumptions on the distribution of the model parameters. They assume that

- the consumption utilities, r , are uniformly distributed,
- advantageous inequity aversion, γ , follows some distribution function $h(\gamma)$, and that
- generosity, λ , and disadvantageous inequity aversion, β , are constant for all consumers.

2 Derivations of Proposition 1 (PAAP, PAYW, and critical costs)

This section is constructed as follows. First, we retrace CKZ's calculations for PAAP. Second, we derive the firm's profit in PAYW and compare our results to the results of CKZ. Third, we derive the critical costs level that equates profits in PAAP and PAYW.

2.1 Derivation and properties of PAAP

2.1.1 Derivation of optimal prices and profits in PAAP

For their Proposition 1 in their Section 2, CKZ derive the firms profits under “pay as asked” pricing (PAAP) and PAYW pricing.

First, CKZ show by contradiction that a seller with pricing power will always charge a posted price, p_{PAAP}^* above the marginal consumer's fair price. They denote the consumption utility for the marginal consumer as \tilde{r} . If the seller's price is lower than the marginal consumer's fair price, r_{i0} , the consumer would experience advantageous inequity aversion. Thus, the marginal buyer's utility would be given by

$$\begin{aligned} u_{\tilde{r}} &= \tilde{r} - p_{PAAP} - \gamma_i(r_{i0} - p_{PAAP}) \\ &= \tilde{r} - p_{PAAP} - \gamma_i(\lambda\tilde{r} + (1 - \lambda)c - p_{PAAP}). \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, as there must be advantageous inequity,

$$\lambda\tilde{r} + (1 - \lambda)c > p_{PAAP}.$$

As the seller is a profit maximizing monopolist, one can assume that the seller will charge prices above costs, i.e., $p_{PAAP} > c$.

Next, $u_{\tilde{r}}$ is set to zero and solved for \tilde{r} to find the critical consumption utility of the marginal consumer.

$$\tilde{r} - p_{PAAP} - \gamma_i(\lambda\tilde{r} + (1 - \lambda)c - p_{PAAP}) = 0$$

$$\tilde{r}(1 - \lambda\gamma_i) = p_{PAAP}(1 - \gamma_i) + \gamma_i c(1 - \lambda)$$

$$\tilde{r} = \frac{p_{PAAP}(1 - \gamma_i) + \gamma_i c(1 - \lambda)}{(1 - \lambda\gamma_i)} := \tilde{r}^+$$

for all $\gamma_i < \frac{1}{\lambda}$ as $(1 - \lambda\gamma_i) > 0$.

As the marginal consumer will buy,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{r}^+ &> p_{PAAP}. \\ \frac{p_{PAAP}(1 - \gamma_i) + \gamma_i c(1 - \lambda)}{(1 - \lambda\gamma_i)} &> p_{PAAP} \\ \gamma(1 - \lambda)(-p + c) &> 0 \\ c &> p_{PAAP}. \end{aligned}$$

This is a contradiction. Hence, there cannot be advantageous inequity for the buyer if the seller sets the price.

Therefore, in PAAP, the consumers will experience disadvantageous inequity, $0 \leq r_{i0} \leq p_{PAAP}$. Thus, the marginal consumer will only buy the product if the consumption utility exceeds the price and the disutility from disadvantageous inequity. In this case (1) will simplify to

$$u_i = r_i - p_{PAAP} - \beta(p_{PAAP} - r_{i0}).$$

By substituting r_{i0} , we get

$$u_i = r_i - p_{PAAP} - \beta(p_{PAAP} - (\lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c)). \quad (3)$$

Note that we are ultimately interested in paying consumers. Therefore, we only need to observe consumers with $r_i > c$ (hence $r_{i0} = (\lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c)$) and can neglect consumers with $r_i \leq c$ (hence $r_{i0} = c$).

The marginal consumer will make a purchase if $u_i \geq 0$. Rearranging (3) and solving for r_i , CKZ arrive at r_i for the marginal consumer

$$r_i = p_{PAAP} + \frac{\beta(1 - \lambda)(p_{PAAP} - c)}{1 + \lambda\beta} := r^+.$$

All consumers with a consumption utility above this threshold, $r^+ \leq r_i \leq 1$, will make a purchase. The firm will earn the price, p_{PAAP} , and has to bear the costs, c . Hence, the seller's profits are given by

$$\pi_{PAAP} = \int_{r^+}^1 (p_{PAAP} - c)\phi(r)dr. \quad (4)$$

(CKZ.2)

As r_i follows a uniform distribution, $\phi(r) = 1$, this is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAAP} &= \int_{r^+}^1 (p_{PAAP} - c)dr \\ &= \frac{(c - p_{PAAP})(p_{PAAP}(1 + \beta) - c\beta(1 - \lambda) - \beta\lambda - 1)}{1 + \beta\lambda}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that we drop index i when we take the seller's perspective (i.e., for segment and profit calculations).

For finding the optimal prices and profits, we take the first derivative, set it to 0 and solve for p_{PAAP} .

$$\pi_{PAAP} \rightarrow \text{Max}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \pi_{PAAP}}{\partial p_{PAAP}} &= \frac{(c - p_{PAAP})(1 + \beta)}{1 + \beta\lambda} - \frac{-1 + p_{PAAP}(1 + \beta) - c\beta(1 - \lambda) - \beta\lambda}{1 + \beta\lambda} \\ &= \frac{-2p_{PAAP}(1 + \beta) + c(1 + \beta) + 1 + c\beta(1 - \lambda) + \beta\lambda}{1 + \beta\lambda} \stackrel{!}{=} 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the optimal price is

$$p_{PAAP}^* = c + \frac{1 + \beta\lambda}{2(1 + \beta)}(1 - c). \quad (5)$$

(CKZ.3)

(AW.3)

This is a maximum, as the second derivative,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAAP}}{\partial (p_{PAAP})^2} = -\frac{2(1 + \beta)}{1 + \beta\lambda} < 0$$

is always negative.

Substituting p_{PAAP}^* in π_{PAAP} , we find the optimal profits

$$\pi_{PAAP}(p_{PAAP}^*) = -\frac{1 - c}{2(1 + \beta)} \left(c(1 + \beta) + \frac{1 + \beta\lambda}{2}(1 - c) - c\beta - \beta\lambda(1 - c) \right) \quad (6)$$

$$- 1) \quad (\text{AW.A1})$$

$$= \frac{(1 - c)^2(1 + \beta\lambda)}{4(1 + \beta)} := \pi_{PAAP}^*. \quad (\text{CKZ.3})$$

Later, CKZ set $\beta = 0$. In this case the optimal profits reduce to

$$\pi_{PAAP}^{\beta=0,*} = \frac{(1-c)^2}{4}. \quad (7)$$

This corresponds to standard monopolistic pricing.

2.1.2 Properties of PAAP

The derivation of the optimal price and profits allows us to determine properties of PAAP with inequity averse consumers.

When we consider p_{PAAP}^* as a function of λ , we find that the price increases linearly in λ ,

$$\begin{aligned} p_{PAAP}^*(\lambda) &= \frac{1 + c(1 + 2\beta) + \beta\lambda(1 - c)}{2(1 + \beta)} \\ p_{PAAP}^*(\lambda = 0) &= \frac{1 + c(1 + 2\beta)}{2(1 + \beta)} \leq p_{PAAP}^*(\lambda = 1) = \frac{1 + c}{2} \\ \frac{\partial p_{PAAP}^*(\lambda)}{\partial \lambda} &= \frac{(1 - c)\beta}{2(1 + \beta)}. \end{aligned}$$

When we consider p_{PAAP}^* as a function of β , we find that the price decreases monotonically with β

$$\begin{aligned} p_{PAAP}^*(\beta) &= \frac{1 + c(1 + 2\beta) + \beta\lambda(1 - c)}{2(1 + \beta)} \\ p_{PAAP}^*(\beta = 0) &= \frac{1 + c}{2} \\ \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} p_{PAAP}^*(\beta) &= \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \left(c + \frac{1/\beta + \lambda}{2(1/\beta + 1)} (1 - c) \right) \\ &= c + \frac{\lambda(1 - c)}{2} \\ \frac{\partial p_{PAAP}^*(\beta)}{\partial \beta} &= \frac{(1 - c)(\lambda - 1)}{2(1 + \beta)^2} < 0. \end{aligned}$$

With respect to the optimal profits, π_{PAAP}^* , we find that profits increase monotonically in λ ,

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAAP}^*}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{(1 - c)^2 \beta}{4(1 + \beta)} > 0$$

and decreases monotonically in β ,

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAAP}^*}{\partial \beta} = \frac{(1 - c)^2}{4} \cdot \frac{\lambda - 1}{(1 + \beta)^2} \leq 0.$$

Furthermore, this permits us to observe π_{PAAP}^* at some critical values,

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAAAP}^*(\lambda = 0) &= \frac{(1-c)^2}{4(1+\beta)} \\
\pi_{PAAAP}^*\left(\lambda = \frac{1}{2+\beta}\right) &= \frac{(1-c)^2 2(1+\beta)}{4(1+\beta)(2+\beta)} \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2}{2(2+\beta)} \\
\pi_{PAAAP}^*\left(\lambda = \frac{2}{3}\right) &= \frac{(1-c)^2(1+2\beta/3)}{4(1+\beta)} \\
\pi_{PAAAP}^*(\lambda = 1) &= \frac{(1-c)^2}{4} \\
\lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \pi_{PAAAP}^* &= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{4}.
\end{aligned}$$

Taken together, this allows us to determine the range of profits as

$$\frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{4} \leq \pi_{PAAAP}^* \leq \frac{(1-c)^2}{4}. \quad (8)$$

2.2 Derivation and properties of PAYW

2.2.1 Derivation of optimal individual prices and profits in PAYW

CKZ show that in PAYW, a consumer can always prevent disadvantageous inequity which is caused by a price above the perceived fair price by paying a lower price. Thus, the buyer's utility function will be given by

$$\begin{aligned}
u_i &= r_i - p_i - \gamma_i (r_{i0} - p_i) & (9) \\
&= r_i - \gamma_i r_{i0} - (1 - \gamma_i) p_i. & (AW.1a)
\end{aligned}$$

Note: As in CKZ, we denote the consumer's individual price as p_i instead of $p_{PAYW,i}$. This little inconsistency is in the interest of a sparse notation. A consumer maximizes its utility by setting the optimal price. The consumer's utility function, u_i , is a linear function in the price, p_i . Thus, the derivative can be positive or negative depending on γ_i . As this is linear in p_i , we find a corner solution.

For $\gamma_i \leq 1$, the consumer maximizes her utility function by paying as little as possible. As negative prices are not feasible, we observe a corner solution: $[p_i^* | \gamma_i \leq 1] = 0$.

For $\gamma_i > 1$, the consumer maximizes her utility function by paying as much as possible. Prices above r_{i0} create disadvantageous inequity which means that our utility function would be invalid. Thus, the consumer pays $[p_i^* | \gamma_i > 1] = r_{i0}$.

Thus, the optimal price is given by

$$p_i^* = \begin{cases} 0 & \gamma_i \leq 1 \\ r_{i0} & \gamma_i > 1 \end{cases}$$

Next, we need to check whether the consumer would purchase with these prices (participation constraint), i.e., whether optimal prices lead to positive utilities. A consumer who would experience negative utility when buying for their optimal price, p_i , chooses the outside option, abstains from buying and receives a utility of $u_i = 0$.

Using the above prices, the utility function simplifies to

$$u_i = \begin{cases} r_i - \gamma_i r_{i0} - (1 - \gamma_i) \cdot 0 & \gamma_i \leq 1 \\ r_i - \gamma_i r_{i0} - (1 - \gamma_i) \cdot r_{i0} & \gamma_i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$= \begin{cases} r_i - \gamma_i r_{i0} & \gamma_i \leq 1 \\ r_i - r_{i0} & \gamma_i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (\text{AW.1c})$$

The consumers will maximize this utility function

$$u_i \rightarrow \text{Max.}$$

We proceed in a stepwise manner.

- 1) We investigate less fair-minded consumers, i.e., $0 \leq \gamma_i \leq 1$. Consumers with a positive utility decide to make a purchase

$$u_i = r_i - \gamma_i r_{i0} \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

$$r_i \geq \gamma_i r_{i0}. \quad (\text{AW.1b})$$

In contrast to PAAP, we need to observe r_{i0} for both $r_i \geq c$ and $r_i < c$.

- a) If $1 \geq r_i > c$, $r_{i0} = \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c$ and

$$r_i \geq \gamma_i (\lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c) \geq 0$$

$$r_i \geq -\frac{(1 - \lambda)c}{\lambda}.$$

This always the case. Thus, $u_i^* \geq 0$, the consumer takes the good and freeloads.

The size of this segment of consumers can be defined as

$$\theta_{PAYW,1} = \int_0^1 \int_c^1 \phi(r) dr h(\gamma) d\gamma,$$

with $h(\gamma)$ the distribution of advantageous inequity. Note that we again drop index i when we take the seller's perspective (i.e., for segment and profit calculations).

b) If $r_i \leq c \leq 0$, it follows that $r_{i0} = c$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &= r_i - \gamma_i c \geq 0 \\ r_i &\geq \gamma_i c. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the consumers freeloader if $r_i \geq \gamma_i c$, i.e., if their consumption utility is high, or if their disutility from advantageous inequity aversion is low. Thus, this segment of freeloaders can be defined as

$$\theta_{PAYW,2} = \int_0^1 \int_{\gamma c}^c \phi(r) dr h(\gamma) d\gamma.$$

If this does not hold, i.e., $0 \leq r_i < \gamma_i c$, consumers do not buy. This segment can be defined as

$$\delta_{PAYW} = \int_0^1 \int_0^{\gamma c} \phi(r) h(\gamma) dr d\gamma.$$

The total segment of freeloaders is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{PAYW} &= \theta_{PAYW,1} + \theta_{PAYW,2} \\ &= \int_0^1 \left[\int_{\gamma c}^c \phi(r) dr + \int_c^1 \phi(r) dr \right] h(\gamma) d\gamma & (12) \\ &= \int_0^1 \int_{\gamma c}^1 \phi(r) h(\gamma) dr d\gamma. & (AW.5) \end{aligned}$$

We name the share of less fair-minded consumers $\omega \in [0,1]$.

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= \theta_{PAYW} + \delta_{PAYW} \\ &= \int_0^1 h(\gamma) d\gamma. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Furthermore, we assume that γ_i is distributed according to some distribution $h_{[0,1]}(\gamma_i)$ in the domain $[0,1]$. Again, we drop index i . This allows us to estimate δ and θ more accurately,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{PAYW} &= \int_0^1 \left[\omega h_{[0,1]}(\gamma) \int_0^{\gamma c} dr \right] d\gamma & (14) \\ &= c\omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} & (AW.6) \\ & & (AW.6a) \end{aligned}$$

with $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$: mean of γ in $[0,1]$ and

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_{PAYW} &= \int_0^1 \left[\omega h_{[0,1]}(\gamma) \int_{\gamma c}^1 dr \right] d\gamma \\ &= \omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}).\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

2) Next, we investigate, more fair-minded consumers $\gamma_i > 1$. In this case,

$$u_i = r_i - r_{i0} \geq 0$$

$$r_i \geq r_{i0}.$$

a) Again, if $r_i > c$, $r_{i0} = \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c$ and, therefore,

$$r_i - (\lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c) \geq 0$$

$$(1 - \lambda)r_i - (1 - \lambda)c \geq 0$$

$$(1 - \lambda)(r_i - c) > 0$$

$$(r_i - c) > 0.$$

This is always the case. Hence, the consumer takes the good and pays her fair price.

b) If $r_i \leq c$, it follows that $r_{i0} = c$. Thus,

$$u_i = r_i - c \geq 0.$$

A contradiction. Hence, the consumer does not buy.

The size of all more fair-minded consumers is given by $(1 - \omega)$.

Having defined different segments, we can move on to the firm's profits from all segments.

The profits are composed of:

- Revenues and costs from fair-minded consumers ($(1 - \omega)$ in size): These consumers pay their fair price r_{i0} and the firm incurs cost, c .
- Costs of freeloaders (θ_{PAYW}): The firm incurs costs of c for all freeloading consumers but does not get any revenue.

This allows us to arrive at the seller's profits,

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW} &= \int_c^1 (1 - \omega)(r_0 - c)\phi(r)dr - c\theta_{PAYW} \\ &= \int_c^1 (1 - \omega)\lambda(r - c)\phi(r)dr - c\omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}).\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

(AW.7)

As the seller cannot influence prices, the optimal profits are given when consumers behave utility maximizing and not require any optimization from the seller. We can solve the integral and arrive at

$$\pi_{PAYW} = \frac{\lambda(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{2} - c\omega(1-c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) := \pi_{PAYW}^* \quad (17)$$

(AW.A.3)

2.2.2 Properties of PAYW

This allows us to determine how the sellers profit change with changes in the model parameters,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW}^*}{\partial \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} &= c^2\omega > 0 \\ \frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW}^*}{\partial \lambda} &= \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2(1-\omega) > 0 \\ \frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW}^*}{\partial \omega} &= -c(1-c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) - \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2\lambda < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Profits of PAYW are increasing with generosity, λ , and the mean of advantageous inequity aversion in $[0,1]$, $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$, and decreasing in the share of less fair-minded consumer, ω .

Furthermore, this allows us to observe π_{PAYW}^* at some critical values,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW}^*(\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = 0) &= \frac{\lambda(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{2} - c\omega \\ \pi_{PAYW}^*(\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = 1) &= \frac{\lambda(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{2} - c\omega(1-c) \\ \pi_{PAYW}^*(\omega = 0) &= \frac{\lambda(1-c)^2}{2} \\ \pi_{PAYW}^*(\omega = 1) &= -c(1-c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \\ \pi_{PAYW}^*(\omega = 1, \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = 0) &= -c. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, profits are in the range of

$$\begin{aligned} -c \leq \frac{\lambda(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{2} - c\omega \leq \pi_{PAYW}^* \leq \frac{\lambda(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{2} - c\omega(1-c) \quad (18) \\ \leq \frac{\lambda(1-c)^2}{2}. \quad (AW.A.5) \end{aligned}$$

2.2.3 Excursus: CKZ's profit calculation

The results derived in Section 2.2.1 deviate from CKZ in Case 1b) of Section 2.2.1. In their paper, CKZ ignore the δ segment and assume that all consumers behave like in Case 1a).

Thus, all less fair-minded consumers freeload.

Therefore, they derive their profits as

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW}^{CKZ*} &= \int_c^1 (1 - \omega)(r_0 - c)\phi(r)dr - c\omega & (19) \\ &= \frac{\lambda(1 - \omega)(1 - c)^2}{2} - c\omega. & (AW.7a) \\ & & (CKZ.4)\end{aligned}$$

CKZ use the term “freeloader” instead of “less fair-minded consumer” for consumers with $\gamma_i \leq 1$. When sticking to their notation and assuming that all less fair-minded consumers are freeloaders, $\omega = \theta^{CKZ}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW}^{CKZ*} &= \int_c^1 (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(r_0 - c)\phi(r)dr - c\theta^{CKZ} & (20) \\ &= \frac{\lambda(1 - \omega)(1 - c)^2}{2} - c\theta^{CKZ}. & (AW.A.2) \\ & & (CKZ.5) \\ & & (CKZ.A.1)\end{aligned}$$

2.3 Comparing PAAP to PAYW

When comparing PAAP to PAYW, we can derive the critical cost level above which PAAP will always be better than PAYW. First, we offer our calculations that include the correct share of freeloaders. Second, we retrace CKZ’s calculations.

2.3.1 Deriving the new c^+

In order to derive the new critical cost level, c^+ for which PAYW is better than PAAP, we compare our updated optimal profit function π_{PAYW}^* to the profits under fixed prices and solve for c :

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW}^* &> \pi_{PAAP}^* \\ \pi_{PAYW}^* - \pi_{PAAP}^* &> 0 \\ \frac{\lambda(1 - \omega)(1 - c)^2}{2} - c\omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) - \frac{(1 - c)^2(1 + \beta\lambda)}{4(1 + \beta)} &> 0 \\ (1 - c)^2(2\lambda(1 + \beta)(1 - \omega) - (1 + \lambda\beta)) - 4c\omega(1 + \beta)(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) &> 0 \\ -A_{COMP}(1 - c)^2 - 4cB_{COMP}(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) &> 0\end{aligned}$$

with $A_{COMP} = 1 - \lambda(2 + \beta - 2\omega(1 + \beta))$ and $B_{COMP} = \omega(1 + \beta)$.

$$\begin{aligned}A_{COMP} - 2A_{COMP}c + A_{COMP}c^2 + 4cB_{COMP} - 4c^2B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} &< 0 \\ c^2(A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) - 2c(A_{COMP} - 2B_{COMP}) + A_{COMP} &< 0. & (21)\end{aligned}$$

We solve using the reduced quadratic equation form,

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{1,2} &= \frac{2(A_{COMP} - 2B_{COMP}) \pm \sqrt{4(A_{COMP} - 2B_{COMP})^2 - 4A_{COMP}(A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]})}}{2(A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]})} \\
&= \frac{2(A_{COMP} - 2B_{COMP}) \pm \sqrt{16B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}))}}{2(A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]})} \\
&= \frac{A_{COMP} - 2B_{COMP} \pm 2\sqrt{B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}))}}{A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} \\
&= 1 - \frac{2B_{COMP}(1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \mp 2\sqrt{B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}))}}{A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} \\
c_1 &= 1 - \frac{2B_{COMP}(1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) - 2\sqrt{B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}))}}{A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} \\
c_2 &= 1 - \frac{2B_{COMP}(1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) + 2\sqrt{B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}))}}{A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}.
\end{aligned}$$

We could also solve (21) by completing the square

$$\begin{aligned}
c^2(A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\gamma) - 2c(A_{COMP} - 2B_{COMP}) + A_{COMP} \\
= (A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\gamma)(c - c_1)(c - c_2) < 0
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

as

$$\begin{aligned}
c_1 &= 1 - \frac{(a - b)}{-d} = 1 + \frac{a - b}{d} \\
c_2 &= 1 - \frac{(a + b)}{-d} = 1 + \frac{a + b}{d}.
\end{aligned}$$

$c_1 < c_2$.

a) When $A_{COMP} = 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$, this does not yield a solution in $c \in [0,1]$ as

$$\begin{aligned}
-2c \cdot 2B_{COMP}(2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} - 1) + 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} < 0 \\
c(1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) + \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} < 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence for

- 1) $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = \frac{1}{2}$, dividing by 0, wid.
- 2) $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} > \frac{1}{2}$, $c > -\frac{\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} = 1 + \frac{-1 + \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} > 1$

$$3) \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} < \frac{1}{2}, c < -\frac{\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{1-2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} < 0.$$

b) When $A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} < 0$, the second part of (22) must be positive, i.e., $(c - c_1)(c - c_2) > 0$, so that the inequality holds.

Therefore, $(c - c_1) > 0$ and $(c - c_2) > 0$, and $c_2 > 0$ as a feasible solution or $(c - c_1) < 0$ and $(c - c_2) < 0$, and, therefore, $c < c_1$. as are interested in the lower cost level, i.e., $c < c_1$. Hence, we can discard c_2 as a possible solution.

Thus,

$$c^+ < 1 - \frac{2B_{COMP}(1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) - 2\sqrt{B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]})}}}{A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} \quad (23)$$

(AW.8)

$$A_{COMP} = 1 - \lambda(2 + \beta - 2\omega(1 + \beta))$$

(AW.A.4)

$$B_{COMP} = \omega(1 + \beta).$$

To find the maximum share of less fair-minded consumers a PAYW seller can tolerate before switching to PAAP, we set c^+ to 0 (costs below 0 are not tolerable).

$$\begin{aligned} c^+ &= 0 \\ 1 - \frac{2B_{COMP}(1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) - 2\sqrt{B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]})}}}{A_{COMP} - 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} &= 0 \\ &= 2B_{COMP}(1 - 2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) - 2\sqrt{B_{COMP}(B_{COMP} - A_{COMP}(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]})}} \\ &= 4A_{COMP}B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}. \end{aligned}$$

As $A_{COMP} = 4B_{COMP}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$ does not yield a meaningful solution for c_1 , this only has a solution for $A_{COMP} = 0$. Therefore,

$$1 - \lambda(2 + \beta) + 2\lambda\omega(1 + \beta) = 0.$$

Thus, our critical threshold is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= \frac{\lambda(2 + \beta) - 1}{2\lambda(1 + \beta)} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\lambda - 1}{2\lambda(1 + \beta)} := \omega^+. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Thus, even for zero costs, for PAYW to dominate PAAP, $\omega \leq \omega^+$. As $\lambda - 1 < 0$, ω^+ is always smaller than $1/2$.

Furthermore, we can use this expression to check conditions for λ so that $\omega^+ > 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}\omega^+ &> 0 \\ \frac{\lambda(1 + \beta) + \lambda - 1}{2\lambda(1 + \beta)} &> 0 \\ \lambda &\geq \frac{1}{2 + \beta}.\end{aligned}$$

Thus, as a necessary condition, λ must be greater than $\lambda \geq \frac{1}{2 + \beta}$ for PAYW to be more profitable than PAAP.

2.3.2 CKZ's c^+

In this section, we retrace CKZ's results. CKZ derive the critical cost level below which PAYW is better than PAAP, c^+ , by comparing the profits of both pricing schemes and solving for c . In their paper, CKZ denote this threshold as c^* . However, as noted above, we reserve *-superscripts for optimal values. Thus, we return to c^{CKZ^+} .

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW}^{CKZ,*} &> \pi_{PAAP}^* \\ \pi_{PAYW}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAAP}^* &> 0 \\ \frac{\lambda(1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - c)^2}{2} - c\theta^{CKZ} - \frac{(1 - c)^2(1 + \beta\lambda)}{4(1 + \beta)} &> 0 \\ \frac{(1 - c)^2}{2} \left(\lambda - \lambda\theta^{CKZ} - \frac{1 + \beta\lambda}{2(1 + \beta)} \right) - c\theta^{CKZ} &> 0 \\ A_{COMP}^{CKZ}(1 - c)^2 - c\theta^{CKZ} &> 0\end{aligned}$$

with $A_{COMP}^{CKZ} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\lambda - \lambda\theta^{CKZ} - \frac{(1 + \beta\lambda)}{2(1 + \beta)} \right)$. Furthermore, $A_{COMP}^{CKZ} > 0$ in order to get a solution for this inequality.

$$A_{COMP}^{CKZ} - 2A_{COMP}^{CKZ}c + A_{COMP}^{CKZ}c^2 - c\theta^{CKZ} > 0.$$

We solve this quadratic equation by using the reduced quadratic equation form,

$$\begin{aligned}A_{COMP}^{CKZ}c^2 + c(-2A_{COMP}^{CKZ} - \theta^{CKZ}) + A_{COMP}^{CKZ} &= 0 \\ A_{COMP}^{CKZ}c^2 + cB_{COMP}^{CKZ} + A_{COMP}^{CKZ} &= 0,\end{aligned}$$

with $B_{COMP}^{CKZ} = -2A_{COMP}^{CKZ} - \theta^{CKZ} < 0$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{1,2} &= \frac{-B_{COMP}^{CKZ} \pm \sqrt{B_{COMP}^{CKZ\ 2} - 4A_{COMP}^{CKZ\ 2}}}{2A_{COMP}^{CKZ}} \\
&= \frac{2A_{COMP}^{CKZ} + \theta^{CKZ} \pm \sqrt{\theta^{CKZ}(4A_{COMP}^{CKZ} + \theta^{CKZ})}}{2A_{COMP}^{CKZ}} \\
c_1 &= 1 + \frac{\theta^{CKZ}}{2A_{COMP}^{CKZ}} + \frac{\sqrt{\theta^{CKZ}(4A_{COMP}^{CKZ} + \theta^{CKZ})}}{2A_{COMP}^{CKZ}} > 1 \\
c_2 &= 1 + \frac{\theta^{CKZ}}{2A_{COMP}^{CKZ}} - \frac{\sqrt{\theta^{CKZ}(4A_{COMP}^{CKZ} + \theta^{CKZ})}}{2A_{COMP}^{CKZ}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, $c_1 > c_2$ and as c_1 is outside of the parameter range, it is not a feasible solution.

We set $D_{COMP}^{CKZ} = 1 + \frac{\theta^{CKZ}}{2A_{PAYW}^{CKZ}} > 1$ for this examination. Thus, we get

$$c_2 = D_{COMP}^{CKZ} - \sqrt{D_{COMP}^{CKZ\ 2} - 1} \geq 0$$

as a feasible solution as long as it does not exceed the upper threshold for costs ($c = 1$).

Thus, for CKZ PAYW is optimal if

$$0 < c < \min(1, c_2)$$

c_2 is equivalent to CKZ's critical threshold:

$$\begin{aligned}
c^{CKZ,+} & \\
&= 1 && (25) \\
&= \frac{\left(2\theta^{CKZ}(1+\beta) - 2\sqrt{\theta^{CKZ}(1+\beta)(\theta^{CKZ}(1+\beta)(1-2\lambda) + \lambda(2+\beta) - 1)}\right)}{1 - \lambda(2+\beta - 2\theta^{CKZ}(1+\beta))}. && (CKZ.6) \\
& && (CKZ.A.2)
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, by solving $A_{COMP}^{CKZ} > 0$ for λ , we can derive the minimum level of generosity that is needed for PAYW being better than PAAP.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{2} \left(\lambda - \lambda\theta^{CKZ} - \frac{(1+\beta\lambda)}{2(1+\beta)} \right) &> 0 \\
\lambda &> \frac{1}{2+\beta - 2\theta^{CKZ} - 2\beta\theta^{CKZ}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, even when the share of freeloaders minimal, $\theta^{CKZ} = 0$, generosity must exceed $A_{COMP}^{CKZ} > \frac{1}{2+\beta}$ for PAYW to be preferred to PAAP.

Furthermore, this also allows us to define the maximum level of freeloaders by setting $A_{COMP}^{CKZ} > 0$ or $c^{CKZ,+} > 0$ and solving for θ^{CKZ} .

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\lambda - \lambda \theta^{CKZ} - \frac{(1 + \beta \lambda)}{2(1 + \beta)} \right) > 0$$

$$\theta^{CKZ} < \frac{2\lambda + \beta\lambda - 1}{2\lambda + 2\beta\lambda}.$$

If we account for the maximum amount of generosity, $\lambda = 1$, we see that the highest tolerable level of freeloaders is

$$\theta^{CKZ} < \frac{1 + \beta}{2 + 2\beta}$$

$$\theta^{CKZ} < \frac{1}{2}.$$

Thus, PAYW can only be better than PAAP if less than half of the consumers freeride.

3 Derivations of Proposition 2 (PAYW-MP)

In this part we first retrace CKZ's calculations with respect to PAYW with the minimum price (PAYW-MP) and show an inconsistency in the derivation of the properties of the minimum price. Second, we elaborate on the extension of PAYW-MP with disadvantageous inequity aversion.

This section introduces a few notational inconsistencies with respect to our symbolic conventions:

- We use \underline{p} to denote the minimum price instead of the longer $p_{PAYW-MP}$.
- Auxiliary variables use a shortened form for PAYW-MP (i.e., MP).
- The upper part of the fair price r_{i0} ($r_i > c$) is denoted p_f , i.e., $p_f = \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c$.

3.1 Derivations and properties for Proposition 2 with $\beta = 0$

In this section, we retrace CKZ's calculations for PAYW-MP. In their paper, they only consider the special case of $\beta = 0$.

3.1.1 Derivation of PAYW-MP for $\beta = 0$

When ruling out disadvantageous inequity, consumer i 's utility function will be given by

$$u_i = r_i - p_i - \gamma_i \max\{p_f - p_i, 0\}, \quad \gamma_i \geq 0. \quad (26)$$

In case the consumer pays the seller's minimum price, \underline{p} , the consumer's utility would be given by

$$u_i = \begin{cases} r_i - \underline{p} & \underline{p} \geq p_f \\ r_i - \underline{p} - \gamma_i(p_f - \underline{p}) & p_f > \underline{p} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

We analyze consumption behavior in a stepwise manner:

- 1) When $\underline{p} > p_f$: Consumers with a positive utility will buy as

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &= r_i - \underline{p} \geq 0 \\ r_i &\geq \underline{p}. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, they will pay their utility-maximizing price. As this is a linear function with a negative slope in \underline{p} , the extremum will be at the lower bound. Therefore, consumers will pay as little as possible, which is the minimum price, \underline{p} .

All other consumers choose the outside option and will refrain from purchasing.

- 2) When $\underline{p} < p_f$: Whenever the consumer's fair price exceeds the minimum price and the consumer pays this minimum price, she will experience advantageous inequity aversion. However, the consumer can choose to set a higher price and evade disutility from advantageous inequity aversion. In this case, the consumer's utility will be similar to PAYW (9):

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &= r_i - p_i - \gamma_i (p_f - p_i) \\ &= r_i - \gamma_i p_f - (1 - \gamma_i) p_i. \end{aligned}$$

In maximizing this their utility with respect to the optimal price, we have a linear function again and, therefore, find a corner solution:

- Consumers with $\gamma_i \leq 1$, $\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial p_i} \leq 0$, will pay as little as possible, which is the minimum price, and bear advantageous inequity aversion. Thus, their utility is given by

$$u_i = r_i - \underline{p} - \gamma_i (p_f - \underline{p})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= r_i - \underline{p} - \gamma_i \left((\lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c) - \underline{p} \right) \geq 0 \\
r^+ &= \frac{\underline{p}(1 - \gamma_i) + c\gamma_i(1 - \lambda)}{1 - \gamma_i\lambda} \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

This is always lower than the \underline{p} because

$$r^+ - \underline{p} = \frac{\underline{p}(1 - \gamma_i - 1 + \gamma_i\lambda) + c\gamma_i(1 - \lambda)}{1 - \gamma_i\lambda} = \frac{(c - \underline{p})\gamma_i(1 - \lambda)}{1 - \gamma_i\lambda} \leq 0,$$

as the seller will not set the minimum price below costs, $\underline{p} \geq c$.

Consumers can only obtain the good when paying at least the minimum price, \underline{p} .

Therefore, only consumers with

$$r_i \geq \underline{p}$$

buy and pay \underline{p} . All others refrain from purchasing.

- For consumers with $\gamma_i > 1$, $\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial p_i} > 0$, therefore, their optimal price is the highest feasible price, i.e., the fair price. Thus, their utility will be given by

$$\begin{aligned}
u_i &= r_i - p_f \\
r_i - (\lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c) &\geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

As shown before, this is always positive.

Thus, the buyer's utility is given by

$$u_i = \begin{cases} r_i - \underline{p} & \underline{p} \geq p_f \\ r_i - \underline{p} - \gamma_i(p_f - \underline{p}) & p_f > \underline{p} \wedge \gamma_i \leq 1. \\ r_i - p_i - \gamma_i(p_f - p_i) & p_f > \underline{p} \wedge \gamma_i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

The critical consumption utility, \underline{r} , that distinguishes consumers who experience advantageous inequity aversion from those who do not (because of $\beta = 0$) can be derived by comparing the minimum price to the fair price and solving for r_i

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{p} &= p_f. \\
\underline{p} &= \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c \\
r_i &= \frac{\underline{p} - (1 - \lambda)c}{\lambda} := \underline{r}.
\end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

For reasons of simplification, we set

$$\underline{r} = \frac{p}{\lambda} - cA_{MP}^{\beta=0}$$

with

$$A_{MP}^{\beta=0} = \frac{1 - \lambda}{\lambda}.$$

(30)

Using this notation, we can set up the profit function for the firm. First, we distinguish between consumers with $\gamma_i > 1$, $(1 - \omega)$ in size and consumers with $\gamma_i \leq 1$, ω in size.

Note: we use ω instead of θ^{CKZ} . This follows from CKZ use of their θ^{CKZ} to describe all consumers with $\gamma_i \leq 1$ instead of freeloaders. However, in PAYW-MP the seller can exclude freeloaders. Thus, these consumers should be labeled less fair-minded consumers, ω .

As discussed before, consumers with $\gamma_i \leq 1$ pay the minimum price when $r_i \geq \underline{p}$ and refrain from purchasing otherwise. Consumers with $\gamma_i > 1$ pay their fair price when $r_i > \underline{r}$, the minimum price when $\underline{r} > r_i \geq \underline{p}$ and refrain from purchasing otherwise, $r_i < \underline{r}$. The firm incurs costs for all buying consumers. As before, we drop the index i when taking the seller's perspective. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0} &= (1 - \omega) \left(\int_{\underline{p}}^{\underline{r}} (\underline{p} - c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{\underline{r}}^1 (p_f - c) \phi(r) dr \right) + \omega \int_{\underline{p}}^1 (\underline{p} - c) \phi(r) dr \\ &= (1 - \omega) \left(\int_{\underline{p}}^{\underline{r}} (\underline{p} - c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{\underline{r}}^1 \lambda(r - c) \phi(r) dr \right) + \omega \int_{\underline{p}}^1 (\underline{p} - c) \phi(r) dr. \end{aligned}$$

To solve the integrals, we use the uniform distribution $\phi(r)$ for r . Thus, $\phi(r) = 1$.

Thus, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0} &= (1 - \omega) \left((\underline{p} - c)^2 A_{MP}^{\beta=0} + \frac{-(\underline{p} - c)^2}{2\lambda} + \frac{\lambda(1 - c)^2}{2} \right) + \omega (\underline{p} - c) (1 - \underline{p}) \\ &= \underline{p}^2 \left(\frac{B_{MP}^{\beta=0}}{2} - \omega \right) + \underline{p} (-cB_{MP}^{\beta=0} + \omega(1 + c)) \\ &\quad + \frac{(1 - \omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1 - 2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 + \lambda(1 - c)^2 \right) - c\omega \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0} &= \frac{-\omega \underline{p}^2}{2\lambda D_{MP}^{\beta=0}} + \underline{p} \left(\frac{c\omega}{\lambda D_{MP}^{\beta=0}} + \omega(1-c) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1-2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 + \lambda(1-c)^2 \right) - c\omega \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} B_{MP}^{\beta=0} &= (1-\omega) \frac{(1-2\lambda)}{\lambda} \\ D_{MP}^{\beta=0} &= \frac{\omega}{2\lambda + \omega - 1} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{CKZ.7})$$

and hence

$$\begin{aligned} B_{MP}^{\beta=0} - 2\omega &= \frac{1-2\lambda-\omega}{\lambda} \\ &= -\frac{\omega}{\lambda D_{MP}^{\beta=0}} \end{aligned}$$

The profit function is a quadratic/linear function in \underline{p} . As discussed before, the optimal minimum price cannot be below costs, $\underline{p} > c$. Furthermore, the minimum price must not be above the highest possible fair price,

$$\begin{aligned} p_f(r_i = 1) &= \lambda + (1-\lambda)c \\ &= c + (1-c)\lambda := p_h \end{aligned}$$

which serves as an upper boundary for \underline{p} . Otherwise, $\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0}$ will be incorrectly defined.

We observe two cases.

- 1) For $\frac{B_{MP}^{\beta=0}}{2} - \omega = 0$, the profit function is linear in \underline{p} . Note that $\frac{B_{MP}^{\beta=0}}{2} - \omega = 0$ implies $\omega = 1 - 2\lambda$ and, therefore, $B_{MP}^{\beta=0} = 2\omega$. Profits are linearly increasing in \underline{p} , the maximum is at the bound and the firm maximizes its profits by setting the highest possible price which is p_h . A higher price would yield infeasible results in the objective function. Thus,

$$\underline{p}_1^{\beta=0,*} = c + (1-c)\lambda. \quad (32)$$

- 2) For $\frac{B_{MP}^{\beta=0}}{2} - \omega \neq 0$, the objective function has a quadratic term. Taking the first derivative yields

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0}}{\partial \underline{p}} = -\frac{\omega \underline{p}}{\lambda D_{MP}^{\beta=0}} + \frac{c\omega}{\lambda D_{MP}^{\beta=0}} + \omega(1-c) \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \quad (33)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{p} &= c + D_{MP}^{\beta=0} \lambda (1-c) \\ &= c + \frac{(1-c)\lambda\omega}{2\lambda + \omega - 1} := \underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{AW.12})$$

Next, we need to check whether this is a local minimum or maximum

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0}}{\partial^2 \underline{p}} = B_{MP}^{\beta=0} - 2\omega \begin{cases} > 0 \rightarrow \text{Minimum} & \underline{p}_2^* < c \\ < 0 \rightarrow \text{Maximum} & \underline{p}_2^* > c \end{cases}$$

Thus, for $B_{MP}^{\beta=0} > 0$ the price $\underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*}$ would lead to minimal profits and the seller is better off charging p_h .

Thus, we can derive conditions for which $\underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*}$ is the optimal price. First, the price must be below the highest possible price,

$$\underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*} \leq p_h. \quad (34)$$

Second, the price must be a local maximum

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0}}{\partial^2 \underline{p}} < 0. \quad (35)$$

Solving (34) for λ gives us $\lambda \geq \frac{1}{2}$.

Furthermore, solving (35) for λ , we find $\lambda > \frac{1-\omega}{2}$. This is always true for $\lambda \geq \frac{1}{2}$. For

$$\frac{1-\omega}{2} < \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}, \underline{p}_1^{\beta=0,*} = p_h \text{ as the optimal price.}$$

We combine $\underline{p}_1^{\beta=0,*} = p_h$ and $\underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*}$ in a single equation

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{p}^{\beta=0,*} &= c + (1-c)E_{MP}^{\beta=0} \lambda \\ \text{where } E_{MP}^{\beta=0} &= \begin{cases} 1 & \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ \omega/(2\lambda + \omega - 1) & \lambda > \frac{1}{2} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Using the optimal minimum price, we can calculate the seller's optimal profits.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0}(\underline{p}^{\beta=0,*}) \\
&= \underline{p}^{\beta=0,*2} \left(\frac{B_{MP}^{\beta=0}}{2} - \omega \right) + \underline{p}^{\beta=0,*} \left(-cB_{MP}^{\beta=0} + \omega(1+c) \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1-2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 + \lambda(1-c)^2 \right) - c\omega \\
&= -\frac{1}{2} \underline{p}^{\beta=0,*2} (2\omega - B_{MP}^{\beta=0}) + \underline{p}^{\beta=0,*} \left(c(2\omega - B_{MP}^{\beta=0}) + \omega(1-c) \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1-2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 + \lambda(1-c)^2 \right) - c\omega \\
&= \underline{p}^{\beta=0,*} (2\omega - B_{MP}^{\beta=0}) \left(-\frac{\underline{p}^{\beta=0,*}}{2} + c \right) + \underline{p}^{\beta=0,*} \omega(1-c) \\
&\quad + \frac{(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1-2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 + \lambda(1-c)^2 \right) - c\omega \\
&= (c + (1-c)E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\lambda)(2\omega - B_{MP}^{\beta=0}) \left(-\frac{(c + (1-c)E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\lambda)}{2} + c \right) \\
&\quad + (c + (1-c)E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\lambda)\omega(1-c) + \frac{(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1-2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 + \lambda(1-c)^2 \right) - c\omega \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (c + (1-c)E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\lambda)(2\omega - B_{MP}^{\beta=0})(c - (1-c)E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\lambda) + c\omega(1-c-1) \\
&\quad + (1-c)^2 \left(E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\lambda\omega + \frac{(1-\omega)\lambda}{2} \right) + \frac{(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1-2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \left(c^2 - (1-c)^2 (E_{MP}^{\beta=0})^2 \lambda^2 \right) (2\omega - B_{MP}^{\beta=0}) - c^2\omega + (1-c)^2 \left(E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\lambda\omega + \frac{(1-\omega)\lambda}{2} \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{1-2\lambda}{\lambda} c^2 \right) \\
&= c^2 \left(\omega - \frac{B_{MP}^{\beta=0}}{2} - \omega + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-2\lambda)}{2\lambda} \right) \\
&\quad + (1-c)^2 \lambda \left(-\frac{(E_{MP}^{\beta=0})^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot \frac{2\lambda + \omega - 1}{\lambda} + E_{MP}^{\beta=0}\omega + \frac{1-\omega}{2} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

For $E_{MP}^{\beta=0} = 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0}(c + (1-c)\lambda) &= (1-c)^2 \lambda \left(-\frac{2\lambda + \omega - 1}{2} + \frac{1+\omega}{2} \right) \\
&= (1-c)^2 \lambda(1-\lambda) := \pi_{PAYW-MP,1}^{\beta=0,*}.
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

For $E_{MP}^{\beta=0} = \frac{\omega}{(2\lambda+\omega-1)}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0} & \left(c + \frac{(1-c)\lambda\omega}{2\lambda+\omega-1} \right) \\
& = (1-c)^2\lambda \left(-\frac{\omega^2\lambda}{2} \frac{2\lambda+\omega-1}{\lambda(2\lambda+\omega-1)^2} + \frac{\omega^2}{(2\lambda+\omega-1)} + \frac{1-\omega}{2} \right) \\
& = (1-c)^2\lambda \left(\frac{\omega^2}{2(2\lambda+\omega-1)} + \frac{(1-\omega)(2\lambda+\omega-1)}{2(2\lambda+\omega-1)} \right) \\
& = \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda(2\lambda+2\omega(1-\lambda)-1)}{2(2\lambda+\omega-1)} := \pi_{PAYW-MP,2}^{\beta=0,*}.
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

Thus, we can summarize,

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0,*} = \begin{cases} (1-c)^2\lambda(1-\lambda) & \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda(2\lambda+2\omega(1-\lambda)-1)}{2(2\lambda+\omega-1)} & \lambda > \frac{1}{2} \end{cases} \tag{39}$$

3.1.2 Properties of PAYW-MP for $\beta = 0$

The derivation of the optimal minimum price allows us to determine the properties of PAYW-MP with $\beta = 0$.

As in CKZ, we observe how the optimal minimum price changes with respect to marginal costs, c , the share of less fair-minded consumers ω and generosity, λ . We proceed in a stepwise manner.

First, we consider $\lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \underline{p}_1^{\beta=0,*}}{\partial c} & = 1 - \lambda \geq 0 \\
\frac{\partial \underline{p}_1^{\beta=0,*}}{\partial \omega} & = 0 \\
\frac{\partial \underline{p}_1^{\beta=0,*}}{\partial \lambda} & = 1 - c > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Second, we consider $\lambda > \frac{1}{2}$,

$$\frac{\partial \underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*}}{\partial c} = 1 + \frac{\lambda\omega}{1-2\lambda-\omega} > 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*}}{\partial \omega} = \frac{(1-c)\lambda(2\lambda-1)}{(1-2\lambda-\omega)^2} > 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{p}_2^{\beta=0,*}}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{(1-c)(-1+\omega)\omega}{(1-2\lambda-\omega)^2} < 0.$$

3.1.3 Excursus: CKZ's optimal prices and profits in PAYW-MP

CKZ present these calculations in their Proofs of Proposition 2 (derivation of the optimal price) and Proposition 4 (derivation optimal profits). These results are notationally somewhat different than our results above.

In their Proof to Proposition 2, they define profits as

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ} = (1-\omega) \left(\frac{\lambda(1-c)^2}{2} + \frac{(1-2\lambda)(\underline{p}-c)^2}{2\lambda} \right) + \theta^{CKZ} (\underline{p}-c)(1-\underline{p}), \quad (40)$$

which corresponds to (31). This allows them to derive optimal minimum prices as

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{p}^{CKZ,*} &= \frac{(\theta^{CKZ}\lambda - (1 - \theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda + \theta^{CKZ}\lambda)c)}{1 - \theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda} \\ &= c - \frac{\theta^{CKZ}\lambda(1-c)}{1 - 2\lambda - \theta^{CKZ}}, \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

which corresponds to (33). In the paper, they name this result \underline{p}^* but later denote it \underline{p} . This is then used to define the optimal minimum price as

$$\underline{p}^{CKZ,*} = \max \left[c, \min \left[\underline{p}^{CKZ}, \lambda + (1-\lambda)c \right] \right]$$

with

$$\underline{p}^{CKZ} = \frac{\theta^{CKZ}\lambda(1-c)}{2\lambda - 1 + \theta^{CKZ}} + c. \quad (42)$$

This result is similar to (36). However, the max/ min combination does not allow the reader to distinguish between high and low generosity settings.

Furthermore, they derive the optimal profits in PAYW-MP in their Proof to Proposition 4,

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} = \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda[1 - 2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda]}{2(1 - \theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda)}. \quad (43)$$

As PAYW-MP allows the seller to exclude all freeloaders at no cost for $\beta = 0$, the misspecification of the freeloader segment discussed in Section 2.2 does not matter and $\theta^{CKZ} = \omega$, we can also write

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} = \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda [1 - 2\omega(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda]}{2(1-\omega-2\lambda)}. \quad (44)$$

This corresponds to $\pi_{PAYW-MP,2}^{\beta=0,*}$, i.e., the profits for $\lambda > 1/2$. Unfortunately, results for $\lambda \leq 1/2$ are omitted by CKZ. This hinders an effective comparison.

3.1.4 Excursus: CKZ's properties of PAYW-MP

In their Proof of Proposition 2, CKZ observe properties of the minimum price by taking the derivatives with respect to c , ω (resp. θ^{CKZ}), and λ . However, they do so only with respect to

$$\underline{p}_2^* = c - \frac{\omega\lambda(1-c)}{1-2\lambda-\omega},$$

i.e., only for $\lambda > 1/2$. This leads to erroneous conclusions: In their Proposition 2, CKZ note “Furthermore, the optimal minimum price [...] decreases with the generosity of fair-minded consumers λ ($\frac{\partial \underline{p}_2^*}{\partial \lambda} < 0$)” (CKZ, p. 784). However, this is only partially true. Even for their optimal price (42), they should get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial c}{\partial \lambda} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial(\lambda + (1-\lambda)c)}{\partial \lambda} &= 1 - c > 0. \end{aligned}$$

These finding changes how we need to look at the minimum price, as there are some cases in which a higher generosity allows a higher minimum price. Unfortunately, CKZ's notation does not allow us to determine conditions under which this is the case. However, as shown above (cf. Section 3.1.2) note that for $\lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{\partial \underline{p}_2^*}{\partial \lambda} > 0$. Obviously, this not a borderline case but holds for half of the considered parameter range. In these cases, increasing generosity allows the seller to increase the minimum price.

3.2 Derivations and properties for Proposition 2 with $\beta \geq 0$

3.2.1 Derivation of PAYW-MP for $\beta \geq 0$

In case of $\beta \geq 0$, we allow for disutility from disadvantageous inequity aversion. Thus, the consumers utility function is given by (1).

In line with CKZ, we assume β_i to be the same for all consumers. Again, the minimum price might be higher or lower than the consumer's fair price. Thus, (1) can also be written as a piecewise function

$$u_i = \begin{cases} r_i - \underline{p} - \beta(\underline{p} - p_f) & \underline{p} > p_f \\ r_i - \underline{p} - \gamma_i(p_f - \underline{p}) & p_f > \underline{p} \wedge \gamma_i \leq 1. \\ r_i - p_i - \gamma_i(p_f - p_i) & p_f > \underline{p} \wedge \gamma_i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

(AW.1d)

Thus, for consumers with $\underline{p} > p_f$, the purchase decision also depends on their disadvantageous inequity aversion. As in PAAP, we calculate the threshold for which the consumer buys as $u_i \geq 0$ and solve for r_i .

$$r_i - \underline{p} - \beta(\underline{p} - (\lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c)) \geq 0 \quad (46)$$

$$r_i \geq \frac{\underline{p} - c\beta + \underline{p}\beta + c\beta\lambda}{1 + \beta\lambda} := r^+. \quad (AW.9)$$

This gives us the critical r^+ for which the consumer still buys with the minimum price \underline{p} .

For further reference, we write more compactly,

$$\begin{aligned} r^+ &= \underline{p} + A_{MP}(\underline{p} - c) \\ &= \underline{p}(1 + A_{MP}) - A_{MP}c \end{aligned}$$

with $A_{MP} = \frac{\beta(1-\lambda)}{1+\lambda\beta}$.

Thus, consumers with $r_i \geq r^+$ buy the product.

The derivations for consumers with $p_f > \underline{p}$ are equivalent to the derivations in Section 3.1.1.

Thus, the profit function can be set up as,

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP} = (1 - \omega) \left(\int_{r^+}^{\underline{r}} (\underline{p} - c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{\underline{r}}^1 \lambda(r - c) \phi(r) dr \right) \quad (47)$$

$$+ \omega \int_{r^+}^1 (\underline{p} - c) \phi(r) dr. \quad (AW.10)$$

Again, we use the uniform distribution, $\phi(r) = 1$, for consumption utilities to solve the integrals

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP} &= (1 - \omega) \left((\underline{p} - c)^2 (B_{MP} - A_{MP}) - \frac{(\underline{p} - c)^2}{2\lambda} + \frac{\lambda(1 - c)^2}{2} \right) \\ &\quad + \omega \left((\underline{p} - c) (1 - \underline{p}(1 + A_{MP}) + A_{MP}c) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \underline{p}^2 \left((1 - \omega) \left(B_{MP} - A_{MP} - \frac{1}{2\lambda} \right) - \omega(1 + A_{MP}) \right) \\
&\quad + \underline{p} \left((1 - \omega) \left(-2c(B_{MP} - A_{MP}) + \frac{c}{\lambda} \right) + \omega(1 + c(1 + A_{MP}) + A_{MP}c) \right) \\
&\quad + (1 - \omega) \left(c^2 \left(B_{MP} - A_{MP} - \frac{1}{2\lambda} \right) + \frac{\lambda}{2}(1 - c)^2 \right) + \omega c(-1 - cA_{MP}) \\
&= \frac{\underline{p}^2}{2\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} (-D_{MP}(1 - \omega) - 2\lambda\omega(1 + \beta)) \\
&\quad + \frac{\underline{p}}{\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} ((1 - \omega)cD_{MP} + E_{MP}\lambda + c\lambda\omega(1 + 2\beta - \beta\lambda)) + F_{MP} \\
&= \frac{\underline{p}^2}{2\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} (-D_{MP} - E_{MP}) \\
&\quad + \frac{\underline{p}}{\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} (D_{MP}c + E_{MP}\lambda + c\omega(1 + \beta\lambda)(1 - \lambda)) + F_{MP} \\
\pi_{PAYW-MP} &= \frac{\underline{p}^2}{2\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} (-D_{MP} - E_{MP}) \\
&\quad + \frac{\underline{p}}{\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} (D_{MP}c + E_{MP}(\lambda + c(1 - \lambda))) + F_{MP}
\end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
B_{MP} &= \frac{1 - \lambda}{\lambda} = A_{MP}^{\beta=0} && \text{(AW.A.6)} \\
D_{MP} &= (2 + \beta)\lambda - 1 \\
E_{MP} &= \omega(1 + \beta\lambda) \\
F_{MP} &= (1 - \omega) \left(\frac{-D_{MP}c^2}{2\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} + \frac{\lambda(1 - c)^2}{2} \right) + \omega c(-1 - cA_{MP}).
\end{aligned}$$

To derive the optimal minimum price, we again distinguish between the linear and the quadratic case of $\pi_{PAYW-MP}$.

The profit, $\pi_{PAYW-MP}$, is linearly increasing in \underline{p} if $D_{MP} + E_{MP} = 0$. Hence optimal profits will be at the corners. Thus, the seller will set the highest possible fair price,

$$p_h = c + (1 - c)\lambda := \underline{p}_1^*. \tag{49}$$

For $D_{MP} + E_{MP} \neq 0$, $\pi_{PAYW-MP}$ is a quadratic function. Thus, to find the global maximum,

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}}{\partial \underline{p}} \stackrel{!}{=} 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{p} &= \frac{D_{MP}c + E_{MP}p_h}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} \\
&= \frac{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})c + E_{MP}(-c + c + (1-c)\lambda)}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} \\
&= c + \frac{E_{MP}(1-c)\lambda}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} := \underline{p}_2^*.
\end{aligned} \tag{50}$$

Furthermore, we check the second derivative to find the local maximum

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAYW-MP}}{\partial^2 \underline{p}} = \frac{-(D_{MP} + E_{MP})}{\lambda(1 + \beta\lambda)} \begin{cases} > 0 & \rightarrow \text{Minimum } \underline{p}_2^* < c \\ < 0 & \rightarrow \text{Maximum } c \leq \underline{p}_2^* \end{cases}$$

Thus, for $D_{MP} + E_{MP} < 0$, \underline{p}_2^* will be a local minimum. As we are looking for a maximum, the seller chooses the highest feasible price $\underline{p}_1^* = p_h$.

For $D_{MP} + E_{MP} > 0$, we will find a local maximum. Thus, the seller will charge \underline{p}_2^* . However, the seller needs to take the upper boundary of p_h into consideration. Thus, \underline{p}_2^* is only valid for

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{p}_2^* &\leq p_h = c + (1-c)\lambda \\
c + \frac{E_{MP}(1-c)\lambda}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} &\leq c + (1-c)\lambda \\
\frac{E_{MP}}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} &\leq 1.
\end{aligned}$$

As $D_{MP} \geq 0$,

$$\lambda \geq \frac{1}{2 + \beta}.$$

Hence \underline{p}_2^* is valid only for high λ . Thus, for $\frac{1-\omega}{(2+\beta+\beta\omega)\lambda} < \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2+\beta}$ the optimal price is $\underline{p}_2^* = p_h$.

Next, we can summarize the optimal minimum price a single piecewise function:

$$\underline{p}^* = c + (1-c)G_{MP}\lambda \tag{51}$$

$$\text{with } G_{MP} = \begin{cases} 1 & \lambda \leq 1/(2 + \beta) \\ E_{MP}/(D_{MP} + E_{MP}) & \lambda > 1/(2 + \beta) \end{cases} \tag{AW.11}$$

$$\tag{AW.A.7}$$

Note that $\frac{E_{MP}}{(D_{MP}+E_{MP})} = \frac{\omega(1+\beta\lambda)}{(2+\beta(1+\omega))\lambda-1+\omega}$.

Finally, we compute the optimal profits under PAYW-MP.

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP}(\underline{p}^*) &= (1-c)^2 \left((1-\omega) \left(G_{MP}^2 \lambda^2 \left(B_{MP} - A_{MP} - \frac{1}{2\lambda} \right) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \omega G_{MP} \lambda (1 - G_{MP} \lambda (1 + A_{MP})) \right) \\
&= (1-c)^2 \lambda \left((1-\omega) \left(G_{MP}^2 \frac{1 - \lambda(2 + \beta)}{2(1 + \beta\lambda)} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + G_{MP} \omega (1 - G_{MP} \lambda (1 + A_{MP})) \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \left(\frac{(1-\omega) G_{MP}^2 (1 - \lambda(2 + \beta)) - 2\omega G_{MP}^2 \lambda (1 + \beta)}{1 + \beta\lambda} + 1 - \omega \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2G_{PAYW-MP} \omega \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \left(\frac{G_{MP}^2}{1 + \beta\lambda} (1 - \omega - \lambda(2 + \beta) + \lambda\omega(2 + \beta) - 2\lambda\omega(1 + \beta)) + 1 \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \omega(2G_{MP} - 1) \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \left(\frac{G_{MP}^2}{1 + \beta\lambda} (1 - \lambda(2 + \beta) - \omega(1 + \beta\lambda)) + 1 + \omega(2G_{MP} - 1) \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \left(\frac{G_{MP}^2 (1 - \lambda(2 + \beta))}{1 + \beta\lambda} + 1 - \omega(G_{MP}^2 - 2G_{MP} + 1) \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \left(\frac{G_{MP}^2 (1 - \lambda(2 + \beta))}{1 + \beta\lambda} + 1 - \omega(G_{MP} - 1)^2 \right) := \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*.
\end{aligned}$$

We set $G_{MP} = 1$ and get

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP,1}(\underline{p}_1^*) &= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \left(\frac{(1 - \lambda(2 + \beta))}{1 + \beta\lambda} + 1 \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda (1 - \lambda)}{1 + \beta\lambda} := \pi_{PAYW-MP,1}^*.
\end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

For $G_{PAYW-MP} = \frac{E_{MP}}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP,2}(\underline{p}_2^*) &= \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{-D_{MP}(E_{MP}/(D_{MP} + E_{MP}))^2}{E_{MP}/\omega} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 1 - \omega \left(\frac{E_{MP} - D_{MP} - E_{MP}}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} \right)^2 \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{-D_{MP}\omega}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} + 1 \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{(1 - (2 + \beta)\lambda)\omega}{(2 + \beta(1 + \omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega} + 1 \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda(2 + \beta) + 2\omega(1 - \lambda) - 1}{(2 + \beta(1 + \omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega} \right) := \pi_{PAYW-MP,2}^*.
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

Thus, the optimal profits are given by

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^* = \begin{cases} \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda(1-\lambda)}{1+\beta\lambda} & \lambda \leq 1/(2+\beta) \\ \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda(2+\beta) + 2\omega(1-\lambda) - 1}{(2+\beta(1+\omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega} \right) & \lambda > 1/(2+\beta) \end{cases}. \tag{54} \quad (\text{AW.A.8})$$

3.2.2 Properties of PAYW-MP for $\beta \geq 0$

3.2.2.1 Properties of the optimal minimum price \underline{p}^*

We derive the derivations of \underline{p}^* with respect to the model parameters c, β, ω and λ .

First, we consider $G_{MP} = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \underline{p}_1^*}{\partial c} &= 1 - \lambda > 0 \\
\frac{\partial \underline{p}_1^*}{\partial \beta} &= 0 \\
\frac{\partial \underline{p}_1^*}{\partial \omega} &= 0 \\
\frac{\partial \underline{p}_1^*}{\partial \lambda} &= (1 - c) > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Second, we consider $G_{MP} = \frac{E_{MP}}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})} = \frac{\omega(1+\beta\lambda)}{(2+\beta(1+\omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega}$.

$$\frac{\partial \underline{p}_2^*}{\partial c} = \frac{D_{MP} + E_{MP}(1 - \lambda)}{D_{MP} + E_{MP}} > 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial p_2^*}{\partial \beta} &= \frac{-\lambda^2 \omega (1-c)(3 + \beta\lambda - 2\lambda)}{(D_{MP} + E_P)^2} < 0 \\
\frac{\partial p_2^*}{\partial \omega} &= \frac{(1 + \beta\lambda)(1-c)\lambda}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})^2} (\lambda(2 + \beta) - 1) > 0 \\
\frac{\partial p_2^*}{\partial \lambda} &= \frac{(1-c)(-2\omega\lambda(1 + \beta) + D_{MP}E_{MP} + E_{MP}^2)}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})^2} \\
&= \frac{(1-c)(-2\lambda\omega - 2\beta\lambda\omega + D_{MP}\omega + D_{MP}\beta\lambda\omega + E_{MP}^2)}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})^2} \\
&= \frac{(1-c)(\omega(D_{MP} - 2\lambda) + \beta\lambda\omega(D_{MP} - 2) + E_{MP}^2)}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})^2} \\
&= \frac{(1-c)(\omega(\beta\lambda - 1) - \beta\lambda\omega + \beta\lambda\omega(a - 1) + b^2)}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})^2} \\
&= \frac{(1-c)(-\omega + \beta\lambda\omega(D_{MP} - 1) + E_{MP}^2)}{(D_{MP} + E_{MP})^2}.
\end{aligned}$$

To determine conditions for $\frac{\partial p_2^*}{\partial \lambda}$ to be positive or negative, we need to consider the nominator as a function of β , λ , and ω ,

$$\begin{aligned}
f(\beta, \lambda, \omega) &= (1-c)(-\omega + \beta\lambda\omega(D_{MP} - 1) + E_{MP}^2) \\
&= (1-c)(-\omega + \beta\lambda\omega((2 + \beta)\lambda - 1) + (\omega(1 + \beta\lambda))^2) \\
&= (1-c)(-\omega + \omega\beta\lambda((2 + \beta)\lambda - 2) + \omega^2(1 + \beta\lambda)^2).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, after cancelling out two terms that are always positive, $(1-c)$ and ω , we obtain:

$$f(\beta, \lambda, \omega) = (-1 + \beta\lambda((2 + \beta)\lambda - 2) + \omega(1 + \beta\lambda)^2).$$

This function f is continuous in β , λ , and ω and increases monotonically with β , λ , and ω .

Therefore, we observe the sign of f at the boundaries of λ ($\frac{1}{\beta+2} \leq \lambda \leq 1$). For the lower boundary, we find

$$f\left(\beta, \frac{1}{\beta+2}, \omega\right) = (1 + \beta\lambda)(-1 + \omega(1 + \beta\lambda)).$$

As $(1 + \beta\lambda)$ is always positive, we must inspect $(-1 + \omega(1 + \beta\lambda))$ only. Solving this term for β and ω we find that the term is positive if

$$\begin{aligned}
\omega &> 1/(1 + \beta\lambda) \\
\beta &> \frac{1 - \omega}{\lambda\omega}.
\end{aligned}$$

For the upper boundary, we find

$$f(\beta, 1, \omega) = (1 + \omega) \left(\beta - \frac{1 - \omega}{1 + \omega} \right) (\beta + 1),$$

As $(1 + \omega)$ and $(\beta + 1)$ are always positive, we must inspect $\left(\beta - \frac{1 - \omega}{1 + \omega} \right)$ only. This will be positive for large β and large ω , i.e.,

$$\omega > \frac{1 - \beta}{1 + \beta}$$

$$\beta > \frac{1 - \omega}{1 + \omega}.$$

3.2.2.2 Properties of the optimal profits $\pi_{PAYW-MP}^*$

We examine the profits with respect to model variables β, λ .

First, we concentrate on disadvantageous inequity aversion, β , and inspect $\lambda \leq 1/(2 + \beta)$.

Thus, take the first derivative,

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*}{\partial \beta} = \frac{(1 - c)^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot \frac{2(\lambda - 1)\lambda}{(1 + \beta\lambda)^2} \leq 0$$

which is monotonically decreasing in β . This also allows to inspect critical values,

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^*(\beta = 0) = (1 - c)^2 \lambda (1 - \lambda)$$

$$\lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^* = \frac{(1 - c)^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot 0 = 0.$$

Second, we turn to $\lambda > 1/(2 + \beta)$ and take the first derivative,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*}{\partial \beta} &= \\ &= \frac{(1 - c)^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot \frac{\left((2 + \beta(1 + \omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega \right) \lambda - (\lambda(2 + \beta) + 2\omega(1 - \lambda) - 1)\lambda(1 + \omega)}{\left((2 + \beta(1 + \omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega \right)^2} \\ &= \frac{(1 - c)^2 \lambda}{2} \frac{\lambda}{\left((2 + \beta(1 + \omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega \right)^2} (2\lambda + \lambda\beta(1 + \omega) - 1 + \omega - 2\lambda(1 + \omega) \\ &\quad - \lambda\beta(1 + \omega) - (2\omega(1 - \lambda) - 1)(1 + \omega)) \\ &= \frac{(1 - c)^2 \lambda^2}{2 \left((2 + \beta(1 + \omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega \right)^2} (-2\lambda\omega - 1 + \omega - 2\omega(1 - \lambda)(1 + \omega) + 1 + \omega) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda^2}{2 \left((2 + \beta(1 + \omega)) \lambda - 1 + \omega \right)^2} (2\omega(-\lambda + 1) - 2\omega(1 - \lambda)(1 + \omega)) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda^2}{2 \left((2 + \beta(1 + \omega)) \lambda - 1 + \omega \right)^2} 2\omega(1 - \lambda)(-\omega) \leq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Which is monotonically decreasing. Once again, we observe the boundaries.

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP}^*(\beta = 0) &= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot \frac{2\lambda + 2\omega(1 - \lambda) - 1}{2\lambda - 1 + \omega} \\
\lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^* &= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \omega}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, we turn to λ .

First, $\lambda \leq 1/(2 + \beta)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*}{\partial \lambda} &= \frac{(1-c)^2}{(1 + \beta\lambda)^2} \left((1 + \beta\lambda)(1 - 2\lambda) - (\lambda - \lambda^2)\beta \right) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2}{(1 + \beta\lambda)^2} (1 - 2\lambda - \beta\lambda^2) \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2}{(1 + \beta\lambda)^2} (1 - \lambda(2 + \beta)) \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Profits are increasing in λ .

Second, $\lambda > 1/(2 + \beta)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP}^* &= \frac{H_{MP}\lambda(I_{MP}\lambda - 2\lambda\omega + 2\omega - 1)}{I_{MP}\lambda + \beta\lambda\omega - 1 + \omega} \\
&= \frac{H_{MP}(J_{MP}\lambda^2 + L_{MP}\lambda)}{K_{MP}\lambda + M_{MP}}
\end{aligned}$$

with $H_{MP} = \frac{(1-c)^2}{2} > 0$, $I_{MP} = (2 + \beta)$, $J_{MP} = b - 2\omega > 0$, $K_{MP} = b + \beta\omega > 0$, $L_{MP} = 2\omega - 1$, $M_{MP} = \omega - 1$.

this allows us to take the derivative,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*}{\partial \lambda} &= H_{MP} \left(\frac{(K_{MP}\lambda + M_{MP})(2J_{MP}\lambda + L_{MP})}{(K_{MP}\lambda + M_{MP})^2} - \frac{(J_{MP}\lambda^2 + L_{MP}\lambda)K_{MP}}{(K_{MP}\lambda + M_{MP})^2} \right) \\
&= \frac{H_{MP}}{(K_{MP}\lambda + M_{MP})^2} (J_{MP}K_{MP}\lambda^2 + 2J_{MP}M_{MP}\lambda + L_{MP}M_{MP}).
\end{aligned}$$

The first term, $\frac{H_{MP}}{(K_{MP}\lambda + M_{MP})^2}$ is always positive. The second term $(J_{MP}K_{MP}\lambda^2 + 2J_{MP}M_{MP}\lambda + L_{MP}M_{MP})$ is positive for $\lambda > 1/(2 + \beta)$, as the term takes the form of a U-shaped quadratic function that is open at the top as $J_{MP}K_{MP} > 0$. As the vertex is in the region $\lambda \leq 1/(2 + \beta)$ as $\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*}{\partial \lambda} \left(\lambda = \frac{1}{2+\beta} \right) > 0$, as

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{H_{MP}}{(K_{MP}\lambda + M_{MP})^2} > 0 \\ & (J_{MP}K_{MP}\lambda^2 + 2J_{MP}M_{MP}\lambda + L_{MP}M_{MP})_{\lambda=1/(2+\beta)} \\ & = 1 - \frac{2\omega}{2+\beta} + \frac{\beta\omega}{2+\beta} - \frac{2\beta\omega^2}{(2+\beta)^2} + \omega - 1 + \frac{2\beta\omega^2}{2+\beta} - \frac{2\beta\omega}{2+\beta} \\ & = \frac{\omega}{2+\beta}(-2 + \beta + 2 + \beta - 2\beta) + \frac{2\beta\omega^2}{(2+\beta)^2}(-1 + 2 + \beta) \\ & = \frac{2\beta\omega^2}{(2+\beta)^2}(\beta + 1) \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*}{\partial \lambda} > 0$ for $\lambda > 1/(2 + \beta)$.

For a better understanding of the profit function, we consider critical thresholds. With respect to λ , for $\lambda \leq \frac{1}{2+\beta}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*(\lambda = 0) &= 0 \\ \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*\left(\lambda = \frac{1}{2+\beta}\right) &= \frac{(1-c)^2}{2(2+\beta)}, \end{aligned}$$

and for $\lambda > \frac{1}{2+\beta}$, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*\left(\lambda = \frac{1}{2+\beta}\right) &= \frac{(1-c)^2}{2(2+\beta)} \\ \frac{(1-c)^2}{3(1+\omega)} &\leq \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*\left(\lambda = \frac{2}{3}\right) \leq \frac{(1-c)^2(1+2\omega)}{3(1+3\omega)} \\ \pi_{PAYW-MP}^*(\lambda = 1) &= \frac{(1-c)^2}{2(1+\omega)}. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, with respect to ω ,

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^*(\omega = 0) = \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2}.$$

Thus, optimal profits are in the range of

$$0 \leq \pi_{PAYW-MP}^* \leq (1-c)^2 \lambda (1-\lambda) \leq \frac{(1-c)^2}{4} \quad \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2} \quad (55)$$

$$\frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{1+\omega} \leq \pi_{PAYW-MP}^* \leq \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} \cdot \frac{2\lambda + 2\omega(1-\lambda) - 1}{2\lambda - 1 + \omega} \quad \lambda > \frac{1}{2} \quad (\text{AW.A.9})$$

4 Derivations of Proposition 3 (PAYW-SP)

The setup of CKZ and AW in PAYW-SP differ with respect to the freeloader segment, i.e., the misspecification discussed in Section 2.2. The more nuanced discussion of the behavior of less fair-minded consumers in AW adds computational complications. Therefore, we start by retracing CKZ's solutions followed by a discussion of AW's solutions.

4.1 CKZ's derivations and properties of Proposition 3

4.1.1 Derivation of PAYW-SP for CKZ

To point to the difference between AW and CKZ which stems from the misspecification of the freeloader segment, we use θ^{CKZ} instead of ω in this subsection.

In PAYW-SP, the consumer cannot be forced to pay something. With a probability of z , the consumer behaves exactly as in PAYW. However, with a probability of $(1-z)$ the consumer adapts the suggested price¹ p_s as her fair price. However, if the perceived price, p_f is higher than p_s , the consumers will continue to hold p_f as their fair price.

Thus, the perceived fair price in PAYW-SP is (with a probability of $(1-z)$)

$$p_{f,s} = \begin{cases} p_s & p_s^u \geq p_f \\ p_f & p_s^u < p_f \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

The variable p_s^u corresponds to p_s , however, the superscript u serves to distinguish the consumer's evaluation of the suggested price from the seller set suggested price.

As before, the consumer will not experience disadvantageous inequity and the consumers utility simplifies to

$$u_i = r_i - p_i - \gamma_i(p_{f,s} - p_i). \quad (57)$$

Maximizing this utility function, we once again find a corner solution. The consumer's price can be the maximum or the minimum depending on γ_i .

¹ Note that we use the subscript s instead of *PAYW-SP* for compactness.

For $\gamma_i \leq 1$, the consumer maximizes her utility function by paying as little as possible. As negative prices are not feasible, we observe a corner solution: $p_i^* = 0$. As CKZ misinterpret the freeloader segment they assume that all consumers buy. However, as shown below this is not correct. Just as in PAYW, some consumers will drop out of the market.

For $\gamma_i > 1$, the consumer maximizes her utility by paying the highest feasible price. Prices above $p_{f,s}$ create disadvantageous inequity which is not captured by the utility function (57). Thus, for $p_s^u \geq p_f$ the consumer pays the maximum feasible price which is $p_i^* = p_s$. For $p_s^u < p_f$ the consumer again pays her maximum feasible price which is $p_i^* = p_f = \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c$. When paying less she would experience disutility from advantageous inequity aversion that outweighs the utility gain from the lower price.

Consumers will only buy if $u_i \geq 0$.

For $p_s \geq p_f$,

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &\geq 0 \\ r_i - p_s - \gamma_i(p_s - p_s) &\geq 0 \\ r_i &\geq p_s. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, as the consumption utility exceeds the suggested price, this consumer segment buys and pays p_s .

For $p_s < p_f$, we are finding the marginal consumer (i.e., the last consumer that still buys) by setting the utility function to zero and solving for r_i ,

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &\geq 0 \\ r_i - p_f - \gamma_i(p_f - p_f) &\geq 0 \\ r_i &\geq \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c \\ r_i &\geq \frac{(1 - \lambda)c}{1 - \lambda} \\ r_i &> c. \end{aligned}$$

This is always the case, as the seller will never suggest a price that is below costs and $p_f > p_s \geq c$ holds in this case. Thus, these consumers always buy and pay p_f .

To distinguish these two cases, we set $p_f \geq p_s$ and solve for r_i

$$\begin{aligned} p_f &\geq p_s \\ \lambda r_i + (1 - \lambda)c &\geq p_s \end{aligned}$$

$$r_i > \frac{p_s - (1 - \lambda)c}{\lambda} := r_s.$$

Thus, consumers with $\gamma_i > 1$ will pay the suggested price if $p_s \leq r \leq r_s$ and the fair price if $r_s < r \leq 1$.

However, if $p_s > p_h$, nobody will pay more than the suggested price. Therefore, for the analysis of the suggested price, we must distinguish two cases,

- 1) $p_s < p_h$ and
- 2) $p_s \geq p_h$.

Before turning to the profit calculations, we need to consider an additional assumption for consumers $c < r \leq p_s^u$, as introduced by CKZ. They assume that disadvantageous inequity aversion is not possible in PAYW-SP. Still, these consumers with low consumption utilities will accept the suggested price only with probability $\frac{1}{2}$ and will set the fair price at r also with probability $\frac{1}{2}$. This gives the following fair price.

$$p_{f,s, c < r \leq p_s^u} = \begin{cases} p_s & \text{with probability } 1/2 \\ r_i & \text{with probability } 1/2 \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

The corresponding utility is given by

$$u_i = r_i - p_i - \gamma_i(p_{f,s, c < r \leq p_s^u} - p_i). \quad (59)$$

For consumers who set p_s as their fair price, the above specifications hold. As postured by CKZ, we let consumers with $\gamma_i \leq 1$ buy. Consumers with $\gamma_i > 1$ will refrain from purchasing as

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &> 0 \\ r_i - p_s - \gamma_i(p_s - p_s) &> 0 \\ r_i &> p_s, \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction as we are in the region $c < r \leq p_s^u$.

For a consumer who sets r_i as her fair price, maximizing her utility,

$$u_i = r_i - p_i - \gamma_i(r_i - p_i),$$

yields another linear function. Thus, the maximum is at the bounds. This can be positive or negative depending on γ_i .

For $\gamma_i \leq 1$ the consumer maximizes her utility function by paying as little as possible. As negative prices are not feasible, we observe a corner solution: $p_i^* = 0$. The consumer will always buy as

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &\geq 0 \\ r_i - 0 - \gamma_i(r_i - 0) &\geq 0 \\ r_i(1 - \gamma_i) &\geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

For $\gamma_i > 1$ the consumer maximizes her utility by paying as much as possible. Prices above $p_{f,s}$, $c < r \leq p_s^u = r_i$ create disadvantageous inequity which means that our utility function would be invalid. Thus, $p_i^* = r_i$. These consumers will buy as the utility

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &\geq 0 \\ r_i - r_i - \gamma_i(r_i - r_i) &\geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

is positive.

Now, we can turn to CKZ's profit calculation. To retrace, we adopt their assumption assumption that all less fair-minded consumers freeload ($\omega = \theta^{CKZ}$).

First, we turn to $p_s < p_h$,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ} &= (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - z) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r - c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{p_s}^{r_s} (p_s - c) \phi(r) dr \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{r_s}^1 (p_f - c) \phi(r) dr \right) + (1 - \theta^{CKZ})z \int_c^1 (p_f - c) \phi(r) dr - \theta^{CKZ}c \\ &= (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - z) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r - c) dr + \int_{p_s}^{r_s} (p_s - c) dr + \int_{r_s}^1 (p_f - c) dr \right) \\ &\quad + (1 - \theta^{CKZ})z \int_c^1 (p_f - c) dr - \theta^{CKZ}c \\ &= (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - z) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r - c) dr + \int_{p_s}^{r_s} (p_s - c) dr + \int_{r_s}^1 ((\lambda r + (1 - \lambda)c) - c) dr \right) \\ &\quad + (1 - \theta^{CKZ})z \int_c^1 ((\lambda r + (1 - \lambda)c) - c) dr - \theta^{CKZ}c \\ &= (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - z) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r - c) dr + \int_{p_s}^{r_s} (p_s - c) dr + \int_{r_s}^1 \lambda(r - c) dr \right) \\ &\quad + (1 - \theta^{CKZ})z \int_c^1 \lambda(r - c) dr - \theta^{CKZ}c \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - z) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{p_s^2}{2} - cp_s + \frac{c^2}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{1 - \lambda}{\lambda} (p_s - c)^2 \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left(\lambda \left(\frac{1}{2} - c + \frac{1}{2\lambda^2} (-p_s^2 + 2cp_s - (1 - \lambda^2)c^2) \right) \right) \right) \\
&\quad + (1 - \theta^{CKZ})z \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda + \frac{c^2\lambda}{2} \right) - \theta^{CKZ}c \\
&= (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - z) \left(p_s^2 \frac{-3\lambda + 2}{4\lambda} + cp_s \frac{3\lambda - 2}{2\lambda} + \frac{c^2}{4} + \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda + \frac{(1 - \lambda)^2 c^2}{2\lambda} \right) \\
&\quad + (1 - \theta^{CKZ})z\lambda \frac{1}{2} (1 - c)^2 - \theta^{CKZ}c.
\end{aligned}$$

To find the optimal suggested price, we take the first derivative with respect to p_s set this to zero and solve for p_s

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ}}{\partial p_s} = (1 - z)(1 - \theta^{CKZ}) \left(\frac{p_s(2 - 3\lambda)}{2\lambda} + \frac{c(-2 + 3\lambda)}{2\lambda} \right) \stackrel{!}{=} 0$$

$$p_s = c := p_{s,1}^{CKZ*}. \quad (60)$$

To check whether this is a minimum or a maximum, we need to check the second derivative,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ}}{\partial (p_s)^2} = \frac{(1 - z)(1 - \theta^{CKZ})(2 - 3\lambda)}{2\lambda}.$$

As $(1 - z)$ and $(1 - \omega)$ are always positive, we must check $\frac{(2-3\lambda)}{2\lambda}$.

$$\frac{(2 - 3\lambda)}{2\lambda} \begin{cases} > 0 \rightarrow \text{Minimum} & \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \\ < 0 \rightarrow \text{Maximum} & \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \end{cases}$$

Thus, if $\lambda < \frac{2}{3}$, the optimal suggested price should be the minimum, i.e., c . Otherwise, the suggested price should be the maximum, i.e., 1. Yet, because of $p_s < p_h$ suggested prices above p_h are not feasible. However, CKZ do not account for this solution. Thus, their optimal profit is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ}(p_s = p_{s,1}^{CKZ*}) &= \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2(1-z)(1-\theta^{CKZ})\lambda + \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2z\lambda(1-\theta^{CKZ}) \\
&\quad - c\theta^{CKZ} \\
&= \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2(1-\theta^{CKZ})\lambda - c\theta^{CKZ} := \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ*}.
\end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

Now, we turn to $p_s \geq p_h$. In this case, no consumer pays more than the suggested price. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ} &= (1-\theta^{CKZ})(1-z) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r-c)\phi(r)dr + \int_{p_s}^1 (p_s-c)\phi(r)dr \right) \\
&\quad + (1-\theta^{CKZ})z \int_c^1 (p_f-c)\phi(r)dr - \theta^{CKZ}c \\
&= (1-\theta^{CKZ})(1-z) \left(-c + \frac{c^2}{4} + \left(1 + \frac{c}{2}\right)p_s - \frac{3p_s^2}{4} \right) + (1-\theta^{CKZ})z\lambda \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2 - \theta^{CKZ}c.
\end{aligned}$$

We take the first derivative and solve for p_s

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ}}{\partial p_s} &= (1-\theta^{CKZ})(1-z) \left(1 + c - 2p_s + \frac{1}{2}(-c + p_s) \right) \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \\
p_s &= \frac{2+c}{3} := p_{s,2}^{CKZ*}.
\end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

We check the second derivative to see whether this is a maximum or a minimum,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ}}{\delta (p_s)^2} = -\frac{3}{2}(1-z)(1-\theta^{CKZ}).$$

This is always negative. Thus, $p_{s,2}^{CKZ*}$ is a maximum.

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ}(p_s = p_{s,2}^{CKZ*}) &= (1-z)(1-\theta^{CKZ}) \left(-c + \frac{c^2}{4} + \frac{1}{3} \left(1 + \frac{c}{2}\right) (2+c) - \frac{1}{12} (2+c)^2 \right) \\
&\quad + (1-\theta)z \frac{1}{2} (1-c)^2 \lambda - c\theta^{CKZ} \\
&= \frac{1}{3} (1-c)^2 (1-z) (1-\theta^{CKZ}) + \frac{1}{2} (1-c)^2 z (1-\theta) \lambda - c\theta^{CKZ} \\
&= \frac{1}{6} (1-c)^2 (1-\theta^{CKZ}) (2 + z(-2 + 3\lambda)) - c\theta^{CKZ} := \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ*}.
\end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

To find whether the firm should charge $p_{s,1}^{CKZ^*}$ or $p_{s,2}^{CKZ^*}$ we check when $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ^*}$ is higher than $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ^*}$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ^*} - \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ^*} > 0 \\ & \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2(1-z)(1-\theta^{CKZ})\lambda + \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2z\lambda(1-\omega) - c\theta^{CKZ} \\ & - \left(\frac{1}{3}(1-c)^2(1-z)(1-\theta^{CKZ}) + \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2z(1-\theta^{CKZ})\lambda - c\theta^{CKZ} \right) > 0 \\ & \frac{1}{2}(1-c)^2(1-z)(1-\theta^{CKZ})\lambda - \frac{1}{3}(1-c)^2(1-z)(1-\theta^{CKZ}) > 0 \\ & \frac{1}{2}\lambda - \frac{1}{3} > 0 \\ & \lambda > \frac{2}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for $\lambda > \frac{2}{3}$, $p_{s,1}^{CKZ^*}$ and for $\lambda \leq \frac{2}{3}$, $p_{s,2}^{CKZ^*}$. Hence, we can collect,

$$p_s^{CKZ^*} = \begin{cases} \frac{2+c}{3} & \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \\ c & \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \end{cases} \quad (64)$$

4.1.2 Properties of PAYW-SP for CKZ

CKZ offer two additional insights in their Proposition 3:

- 1) $p_s^{CKZ^*}$ increases with costs
- 2) $p_s^{CKZ^*}$ is higher when fair-minded consumers are not sufficiently generous.

It is easy to show that this is true.

Ad 1) The first derivative,

$$\frac{dp_s^{CKZ^*}}{dc} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} & \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \\ 1 & \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \end{cases}$$

is always larger 0.

Ad 2) we check

$$p_{s,2}^{CKZ^*} > p_{s,1}^{CKZ^*}$$

$$\frac{2+c}{3} > c$$

$$1 > c$$

which is always the case.

Due to CKZ's condensed notation in their Proof of Proposition 3, we cannot retrace their exact calculations. However, their main results, p_s^{CKZ*} and $\pi_{PAYW-SP}^{CKZ*}$ correspond to our results.

4.2 The solution with the correct share of freeloader

4.2.1 Derivations of PAYW-SP

Our calculations do not differ from those of CKZ for consumers with $\gamma_i > 1$. As discussed before, for less fair-minded consumers ($\gamma_i \leq 1$) who consider the price suggestion (which is the case with probability $(1 - z)$) we find $p_i = 0$.

For $p_s \geq p_f$, consumers maximize their utility,

$$u_i \geq 0$$

$$r_i - 0 - \gamma_i(p_s - 0) \geq 0$$

$$r_i \geq \gamma_i p_s.$$

Thus, consumers with $r_i \geq \gamma_i p_s$ freeload. Consumers with $r_i < \gamma_i p_s$ do not purchase.

For $p_s < p_f$,

$$u_i \geq 0$$

$$r_i - 0 - \gamma_i(p_f - 0) \geq 0$$

$$r_i \geq \frac{(1-\lambda)c}{1-\lambda}$$

$$r_i > c.$$

This is always the case as $c \leq p_s < p_f$, therefore all consumers in this region freeload (cf. Akbari and Wagner 2020).

Thus, all consumers with $r_i \geq \gamma_i p_s$ freeload and we can define the segment of freeloader for those consumers who consider the price suggestion as:

$$\theta_s^{1-z} = (1-z) \int_0^1 \int_{\gamma p_s}^1 \phi(r) h(\gamma) dr d\gamma = (1-z)\omega(1 - p_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}). \quad (65)$$

(AW.5b)

The share of freeloader for consumers who ignore the price suggestion is the same as in PAYW,

$$\theta = \int_0^1 \int_{\gamma c}^1 \phi(r) h(\gamma) dr d\gamma.$$

Thus, the size of the freeloader segment for those consumers who ignore the price suggestion is given by

$$\theta_s^z = z \int_0^1 \int_{\gamma c}^1 \phi(r) h(\gamma) dr d\gamma = z\omega(1 - c \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}). \quad (66)$$

(AW.5a)

The total freeloader segment is given by

$$\theta_s = \theta_s^{1-z} + \theta_s^z.$$

This allows us to determine profits. As before, we have to distinguish two cases:

- 1) $p_s < p_h$ and
- 2) $p_s \geq p_h$.

First, we discuss the case $p_s \leq p_h$.

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1} =$$

$$(1-z) \left((1-\omega) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r-c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{p_s}^{r_s} (p_s-c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{r_s}^1 \lambda(r-c) \phi(r) dr \right) \right. \\ \left. + z(1-\omega) \int_c^1 \lambda(r-c) \phi(r) dr - c\theta_s \right)$$

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1} =$$

$$(1-z) \left((1-\omega) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r-c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{p_s}^{r_s} (p_s-c) \phi(r) dr \right. \right. \quad (67)$$

$$\left. \left. + \int_{r_s}^1 \lambda(r-c) \phi(r) dr \right) \right) + z(1-\omega) \int_c^1 \lambda(r-c) \phi(r) dr \quad (AW.13a)$$

$$- c(\theta_s^{1-z} + \theta_s^z).$$

Using the uniform distribution, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-SP,1} = & \\ (1-z) & \left((1-\omega) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{p_s^2}{2} - cp_s + \frac{c^2}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{1-\lambda}{\lambda} (p_s - c)^2 \right) + \lambda \left(\frac{1}{2} - c - \frac{r_s^2}{2} + cr_s \right) \right) \right. \\ & \left. - c\omega(1 - p_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \right) + z \left((1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\omega(1 - c \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

To find the optimal suggested price, we omit the terms that do not include p_s , i.e., all cases in which $z > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0} &= (1-\omega) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{p_s^2}{2} - cp_s + \frac{c^2}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{1-\lambda}{\lambda} (p_s - c)^2 \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \lambda \left(\frac{1}{2} - c - \frac{r_s^2}{2} + cr_s \right) \right) - c\omega(1 - p_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \tag{68} \\ &= (1-\omega) \left(p_s^2 \frac{-3\lambda + 2}{4\lambda} + cp_s \frac{3\lambda - 2}{2\lambda} + \frac{c^2}{4} + \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda + \frac{(1-\lambda)^2 c^2}{2\lambda} \right) \\ & \quad - c\omega(1 - p_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}). \tag{AW.A.10} \end{aligned}$$

Again, we can make a case distinction. We get a linear term by setting $\lambda = \frac{2}{3}$. For $\lambda \neq \frac{2}{3}$,

$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}$ has a quadratic form.

First, we examine the linear case.

$$\frac{\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0} \left(\lambda = \frac{2}{3} \right)}{\partial p_s} = c \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \omega.$$

In this case, the seller should set the maximum suggested price. As p_s cannot exceed r_s in this setting, the seller will use the maximum $r_s = 1$ and solve for p_s .

$$\begin{aligned} r_s &= 1 \\ \frac{p_s - (1-\lambda)c}{\lambda} &= 1 \\ p_s &= c + (1-c)\lambda \\ &= c + \frac{2}{3}(1-c) \\ &= \frac{2+c}{3} := p_{s,1a}^*. \end{aligned} \tag{69}$$

In case $\lambda \neq \frac{2}{3}$, we take the first derivative,

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}}{\partial p_s} = \left(\frac{p_s(2-3\lambda)}{2\lambda} + \frac{c(-2+3\lambda)}{2\lambda} \right) (1-\omega) + c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}\omega \stackrel{!}{=} 0$$

And solve for p_s

$$\begin{aligned} p_s &= \frac{2\lambda c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{(3\lambda-2)(1-\omega)} \\ &= c + \frac{2\lambda A_s}{3\lambda-2} := p_{s,1b}^* \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

with $A_s = \frac{c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{1-\omega}$. To check whether we have a local minimum or maximum, we take the second derivative:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}}{\partial^2 p_s} = \frac{(2-3\lambda)(1-\omega)}{2\lambda}.$$

Again, as $(1-\omega)$ is always positive, we must check $\frac{(2-3\lambda)}{2\lambda}$.

$$\frac{(2-3\lambda)}{2\lambda} \begin{cases} > 0 \rightarrow \text{Minimum} & \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \\ < 0 \rightarrow \text{Maximum} & \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \end{cases}$$

Thus, if $\lambda \leq \frac{2}{3}$, the optimal suggested price should be the corner solution, c .

If $\lambda > \frac{2}{3}$, the optimal suggested price should be $p_{s,1b}^*$ as

$$\begin{aligned} c &\leq p_s \leq p_h \\ c &\leq c + \frac{2\lambda A_s}{3\lambda-2} \leq c + (1-c)\lambda. \end{aligned}$$

As proof, we check the lower bound

$$c \leq c + \frac{2\lambda A_s}{3\lambda-2}.$$

This is always positive as $c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \geq 0$ and $A_s > 0$ for $\lambda > \frac{2}{3}$.

Next, we check the upper bound,

$$\begin{aligned} c + \frac{2\lambda A_s}{3\lambda-2} &\leq c + (1-c)\lambda \\ \frac{2A_s}{1-c} &\leq 3\lambda-2 \\ \lambda &\geq \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{A_s}{1-c} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for large λ , $p_{s,1b}^*$ is optimal.

For $\frac{2}{3} \leq \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{A_s}{1-c} \right)$ the optimal suggested price will be

$$\begin{aligned}
p_s &= p_h \\
&= c + (1 - c)\lambda := p_{s,1c}^*
\end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

Note: we have to ensure $\lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{A_s}{1-c}\right) \leq 1$ and, thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(1 + \frac{A_s}{1-c}\right) &\leq \frac{3}{2} \\
B_s = \frac{A_s}{1-c} &< \frac{1}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the optimal price for $p_s > p_h$ is

$$p_{s,1}^* = \begin{cases} c & \lambda < \frac{2}{3} \\ \frac{2+c}{3} & \lambda = \frac{2}{3} \\ c + (1-c)\lambda & \frac{2}{3} \leq \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3}(1+B_s) \wedge B_s < \frac{1}{2} \\ c + \frac{2\lambda A_s}{3\lambda - 2} & \lambda > \frac{2}{3}(1+B_s) \end{cases} \tag{72}$$

(AW.A.11)

This allows us to determine optimal profits under $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}$ (consumers who ignore the price suggestion are still disregarded)

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}(c) &= (1-\omega) \left(c^2 \frac{-3\lambda + 2}{4\lambda} + c^2 \frac{3\lambda - 2}{2\lambda} + \frac{c^2}{4} + \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda + \frac{(1-\lambda)^2 c^2}{2\lambda} \right) \\
&\quad - c\omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \\
&= (1-\omega) \left(\frac{c^2}{4\lambda} (-3\lambda + 2 + 6\lambda - 4 + \lambda + 2 - 4\lambda + 2\lambda^2) + \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda \right) \\
&\quad - c\omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \\
&= (1-\omega) \left(\frac{c^2 \lambda}{2} + \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda \right) - c\omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \\
&= (1-\omega) \frac{\lambda}{2} (1-c)^2 - c\omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}).
\end{aligned} \tag{73}$$

The profits with, $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}(c + (1-c)\lambda)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}(c + (1-c)\lambda) & \\
&= \frac{1}{4\lambda} \left((-1+c) \left(\lambda(-4 + (10-3\lambda)\lambda) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + c(-2+\lambda)(2+\lambda(-4+3\lambda)) \right) \right) (-1+\omega) \\
&\quad - 4c\lambda(1+c\gamma(-1+\lambda) - \gamma\lambda)\omega.
\end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

For $2(1+B_s)/3 \leq \lambda$ only $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}$ is valid. This is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \pi_{PAYW-SP,1} \left(c + \frac{2\lambda A_s}{3\lambda - 2} \right) \tag{75} \\
&= (1 - \omega) \left(-\frac{D_s}{2} \left(c + \frac{A_s}{D_s} \right)^2 + c \left(c + \frac{A_s}{D_s} \right) D_s + \frac{c^2}{4} + \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda + \frac{(1 - \lambda)^2 c^2}{2\lambda} \right) \\
&\quad - c\omega \left(1 - \left(c + \frac{A_s}{D_s} \right) \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \right) \\
&= (1 - \omega) \left(-\frac{A_s^2}{2D_s} + \frac{c^2}{4} \left(2D_s + 1 + \frac{2(1 - \lambda)^2}{\lambda} \right) + \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda \right) \\
&\quad - c\omega \left(1 - \left(c + \frac{A_s}{D_s} \right) \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \right) \\
&= (1 - \omega) \left(-\frac{\lambda A_s^2}{3\lambda - 2} + \frac{\lambda}{2} (1 - c)^2 \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \left(c + \frac{2\lambda A_s}{3\lambda - 2} \right) \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

with $D_s = (3\lambda - 2)/(2\lambda)$.

Next, we discuss the case $p_h < p_s$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,2} &= (1 - z) \left((1 - \omega) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_c^{p_s} (r - c) \phi(r) dr + \int_{p_s}^1 (p_s - c) \phi(r) dr \right) \right) \tag{76} \\
&\quad + z(1 - \omega) \int_c^1 \lambda(r - c) \phi(r) dr - c(\theta_s^{1-z} + \theta_s^z). \tag{AW.13b}
\end{aligned}$$

For the uniform distribution of r , $\phi(r) = 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,2} &= (1 - z) \left((1 - \omega) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{p_s^2}{2} - cp_s + \frac{c^2}{2} \right) + (p_s - c)(1 - p_s) \right) - c\omega(1 - p_s \bar{\gamma}) \right) \\
&\quad + z \left((1 - \omega)(1 - c)^2 \frac{\lambda}{2} - c\omega(1 - c \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

For finding the optimal price, we again only consider the terms that include p_s (i.e., set z to zero). This gives us

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0} &= (1 - \omega) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{p_s^2}{2} - cp_s + \frac{c^2}{2} \right) + (p_s - c)(1 - p_s) \right) \tag{77} \\
&\quad - c\omega(1 - p_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \tag{AW.A.12} \\
&= (1 - \omega) \left(\frac{-3}{4} p_s^2 + p_s \left(1 + \frac{c}{2} \right) + \frac{c^2}{4} - c \right) - c\omega(1 - p_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}).
\end{aligned}$$

To find the optimum, we take the first derivative and set it to zero,

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}}{\partial p_s} = (1 - \omega) \left(1 + \frac{c}{2} - \frac{3p}{2} \right) + c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}\omega \stackrel{!}{=} 0.$$

Next, we solve for p_s

$$\begin{aligned} p_s &= \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{c}{2} + \frac{c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{1 - \omega} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{3} (2 + c + 2A_s) := p_{s,2a}^*. \end{aligned} \tag{78}$$

The second derivative indicates that the extremum is a maximum,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}}{\partial p_s^2} = \frac{-3}{2} < 0.$$

However, we must

- a) make sure that $r_s \geq 1$ (otherwise, we would be in condition $\pi_{PAYW-SP}^1$) and
- b) that the suggested price is not higher than the highest possible price, i.e., $p_{s,2}^* \leq 1$.

Ad a)

$$\begin{aligned} r_s &= \frac{1}{\lambda} (p_s - (1 - \lambda)c) \geq 1 \\ \frac{1}{\lambda} \left(\frac{1}{3} (2 + c + 2A_s) - (1 - \lambda)c \right) &\geq 1 \\ \lambda &\leq \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{A_s}{(1 - c)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for $\lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{A_s}{(1 - c)} \right) \leq 1$, the optimal price is given by $p_{s,2a}^*$.

Ad b) Furthermore, we have to check the upper boundary,

$$\begin{aligned} p_{s,2a}^* &\leq 1 \\ \frac{1}{3} (2 + c + 2A_s) &\leq 1 \\ A_s &\leq \frac{1 - c}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for

$$A_s > \frac{1 - c}{2},$$

the seller would like to set an infeasible suggested price, $p_{s,2a}^* > 1$. Therefore, the price is set at the upper limit,

$$p_{s,2b}^* = 1. \quad (79)$$

This also ensures that we do not exceed the upper boundary for λ ,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &\leq 1 \\ \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{A_s}{(1-c)} \right) &\leq 1 \\ A_s &\leq \frac{(1-c)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

We can collect

$$p_s^{(2)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } B_s > 1/2 \\ (2+c+2B_s(1-c))/3 & \text{if } \lambda \leq 2(1+B_s)/3 \text{ and } B_s \leq 1/2 \end{cases} \quad (80) \quad (\text{AW.A.13})$$

Thus, we can define optimal profits under $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}$ (consumers who ignore the price suggestion are still disregarded, $z = 0$),

$$\begin{aligned} &\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0} \left(\frac{1}{3} (2+c+2A_s) \right) \\ &= (1-\omega) \left(-\frac{((2+c)^2 + 4(2+c)A_s + 4A_s^2)}{12} + \frac{((2+c)+2A_s)(2+c)}{6} + \frac{c^2}{4} - c \right) \\ &\quad - c\omega \left(1 - \frac{(2+c+2A_s)\bar{y}_{[0,1]}}{3} \right) \\ &= (1-\omega) \frac{(-(2+c)^2 - 4(2+c)A_s - 4A_s^2 + 2(2+c)^2 + 4(2+c)A_s + 3c^2 - 12c)}{12} \\ &\quad - c\omega \left(1 - \frac{(2+c+2A_s)\bar{y}_{[0,1]}}{3} \right) \\ &= (1-\omega) \left(\frac{1}{12} (4 - 8c + 4c^2 - 4A_s^2) \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \frac{(2+c+2A_s)\bar{y}_{[0,1]}}{3} \right) \\ &\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0} \left(\frac{1}{3} (2+c+2A_s) \right) \\ &= (1-\omega) \left(\frac{(1-c)^2}{3} - \frac{A_s^2}{3} \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \frac{(2+c+2A_s)\bar{y}_{[0,1]}}{3} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (81)$$

For $B_s > 1/2$

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}(p_{s,2b}^* = 1) &= \left((1-\omega) \left(\frac{-3}{4} + \left(1 + \frac{c}{2}\right) + \frac{c^2}{4} - c \right) - c\omega(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{4}(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 - c\omega(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \right).\end{aligned}\quad (82)$$

Next, we check which pricing scheme, $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}$ or $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}$ is optimal for the seller. We follow a piecewise procedure.

For $\lambda < 2/3$, we have to compare $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}(p_s = c)$ to $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}\left(p_s = \frac{1}{3}(2+c+2A_s)\right)$.

Now, we compare the two profit functions

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}(c) - \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}\left(\frac{2+c+2A_s}{3}\right) &= \left((1-\omega) \frac{\lambda}{2}(1-c)^2 - c\omega(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) \right) \\ &\quad - \left((1-\omega) \left(\frac{(1-c)^2}{3} - \frac{A_s^2}{3} \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \frac{(2+c+2A_s)\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{3} \right) \right) \\ &= (1-\omega) \left((1-c)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \right) + \frac{A_s^2}{3} \right) - c\omega \left(1 - c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} - 1 + \frac{(2+c+2A_s)\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{3} \right) \\ &= (1-\omega) \left((1-c)^2 \frac{3\lambda-2}{6} + \frac{A_s^2}{3} \right) - \frac{2}{3}A_s(1-\omega)((1-c) + A_s) \\ &= (1-\omega) \left((1-c)^2 \frac{3\lambda-2}{6} - \frac{A_s^2}{3} - \frac{2}{3}A_s(1-c) \right) < 0.\end{aligned}$$

This is the case as $\lambda < 2/3$ and therefore $3\lambda - 2 < 0$.

Next, we check which profit is optimal at $\lambda = 2/3$.

The profits for $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}$ are given above (74).

Thus, comparing $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}$ to $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}\left(\frac{2+c}{3}\right) - \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}\left(\frac{2+c+2A_s}{3}\right) &= (1-\omega) \left(\frac{A_s^2}{3} \right) - c\omega \left(-\frac{2+c}{3}\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} + \frac{(2+c+2A_s)\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{3} \right) \\ &= (1-\omega) \left(\frac{A_s^2}{3} \right) - A(1-\omega) \frac{2A_s}{3}\end{aligned}$$

$$= (1 - \omega) \frac{A_s^2}{3} (1 - 2) < 0.$$

Thus, $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}$ is always preferred.

For $2(1 + B_s)/3 \leq \lambda$, only $\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}$ is valid.

Contrarily, for $A_s > \frac{1-c}{2}$, only $\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}$ is valid.

Thus, we can conclude,

$$p_s^* = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } B_s > 1/2 \\ (2 + c + 2B_s(1 - c))/3 & \text{if } 0 \leq \lambda \leq 2(1 + B_s)/3 \text{ and } B_s \leq 1/2 \\ (c + 2\lambda B_s(1 - c)/(3\lambda - 2)) & \text{if } 2(1 + B_s)/3 \leq \lambda \leq 1 \text{ and } B_s \leq 1/2 \end{cases} \quad (83)$$

$$(AW.14)$$

$$\text{with } B_s = c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}/((1 - c)(1 - \omega)). \quad (AW.A.14)$$

Combining equations, we can collect the final optimal profits under PAYSW-SP. In contrast to previous deviations, we also need to take the consumers who ignore the price suggestion into account.

For $B_s > 1/2$, we use (89)

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1a}(p_s = 1) = (1 - \omega)(1 - c)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda z}{2} + \frac{1}{4}(1 - z) \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + (1 - z)) \right).$$

For $0 \leq \lambda \leq 2(1 + B_s)/3$ and $B_s \leq 1/2$, we use (81)

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}(p_s = (2 + c + 2B_s(1 - c))/3) \\ = (1 - \omega)(1 - c)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda z}{2} + \left(\frac{1 - B_s^2}{3} \right) (1 - z) \right) \\ - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \left(cz + \frac{(2 + c + 2B_s(1 - c))}{3} (1 - z) \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, for $2(1 + B_s)/3 \leq \lambda \leq 1$ and $B_s \leq 1/2$, profits are given by using (75)

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP,1} & \left(p_s = c + \frac{2\lambda B_s(1-c)}{3\lambda-2} \right) \\
& = (1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda z}{2} + \lambda \left(-\frac{B_s^2}{3\lambda-2} + \frac{1}{2} \right) (1-z) \right) \\
& \quad - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \left(cz + \left(c + \frac{2\lambda B_s(1-c)}{3\lambda-2} \right) (1-z) \right) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we can collect,

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^* = (1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda z}{2} + g_{1\lambda}(1-z) \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + g_{2\lambda}(1-z)) \right) \quad (84)$$

with

(AW.A.15)

$$\begin{cases}
g_{1\lambda} = 1/4 \wedge g_{2\lambda} = 1 & \text{if } B_s > 1/2 \\
g_{1\lambda} = (1-B_s^2)/3 \wedge g_{2\lambda} = (2+c+2B_s(1-c))/3 & \text{if } 0 \leq \lambda \leq 2(1+B_s)/3 \text{ and } B_s \leq 1/2. \\
g_{1\lambda} = \lambda(-B_s^2/(3\lambda-2) + 1/2) \wedge g_{2\lambda} = c + (2\lambda B_s(1-c))/(3\lambda-2) & \text{if } 2(1+B_s)/3 \leq \lambda \leq 1 \text{ and } B_s \leq 1/2
\end{cases}$$

4.2.2 Properties of PAYW-SP

4.2.2.1 Properties of the optimal suggested price p_s^*

How does the price change with the change in the model parameters? In order to answer this question, we take the partial derivatives of the optimal prices. p_s^* .

When $B_s > 1/2$, $p_s^* = 1$. Thus, the partial derivatives are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial c} & = 0 \\
\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \lambda} & = 0 \\
\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \omega} & = 0 \\
\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} & = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

When $0 \leq \lambda \leq 2(1+B_s)/3$ and $B_s \leq 1/2$, $p_s^* = \frac{1}{3} \left(2 + c + 2 \frac{c\omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{1-\omega} \right)$. Thus, the partial derivatives are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial c} & = \frac{1}{3} \left(1 + \frac{2\omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{1-\omega} \right) > 0 \\
\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \lambda} & = 0
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \omega} = \frac{2c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{3} \frac{1}{(1-\omega)^2} > 0$$

$$\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} = \frac{2c\omega}{3(1-\omega)} > 0.$$

When $2(1 + B_s)/3 \leq \lambda \leq 1$ and $B_s \leq 1/2$, $p_s^* = c + \frac{2\lambda c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{(3\lambda-2)(1-\omega)}$. Thus, the partial derivatives are given by

$$\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial c} = 1 + \frac{2\lambda\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{(3\lambda-2)(1-\omega)} > 0$$

$$\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{2c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{(1-\omega)} \frac{-2}{(3\lambda-2)^2} < 0$$

$$\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \omega} = \frac{2\lambda c\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{(3\lambda-2)} \frac{1}{(1-\omega)^2} > 0$$

$$\frac{\partial p_s^*}{\partial \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} = \frac{2\lambda c\omega}{(3\lambda-2)(1-\omega)} > 0.$$

4.2.2.2 Properties of the optimal profits $\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*$

Next, we examine the profits with respect to model variables $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$ and λ . As we are interested in the change due to the suggested price, we set $z = 0$, all consumers consider the suggested price.

- 1) First, we consider $B_s > \frac{1}{2}$. Therefore, there are some restrictions on parameters in the model,

$$B_s = \frac{c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{(1-c)(1-\omega)} > \frac{1}{2}$$

$$1 \geq \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} > \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2c\omega} \wedge c, \omega > 0$$

and consequently,

$$2c\omega > (1-c)(1-\omega).$$

Therefore,

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(p_s^* = 1) = (1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \frac{1}{4} - c\omega(1-\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}).$$

This is linear in $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$, thus, we find a corner solution: profits increase in $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$.

Profits will be lowest for $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^{\min} = \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2c\omega}$ and highest for $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^{\max} = 1$. Thus, profits will be in the region,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{4} - c\omega \left(1 - \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2c\omega}\right) &\leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(p_s^*) \leq \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{4} \\
\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{4} - c\omega + \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2} &\leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(p_s^*) \leq \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{4} \\
\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)(3-c)}{4} - c\omega &\leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(p_s^*) \leq \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{4}
\end{aligned} \tag{85}$$

2) Second, we consider $0 \leq \lambda \leq 2(1+B_s)/3 \wedge B_s \leq 1/2$, and check how optimal profits change in $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$, the profits are given by

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(p_s^*) = (1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \frac{(1-B_s^2)}{3} - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \frac{2+c+2B_s(1-c)}{3}\right)$$

as $B_s = \frac{c\omega\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}}{(1-c)(1-\omega)}$ contains $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$, we rearrange terms,

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) = E_s(1 - F_s^2 \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^2) - c\omega + G_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} + H_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^2$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
E_s &= \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{3} \\
F_s &= \frac{c\omega}{(1-c)(1-\omega)} \\
G_s &= \frac{c\omega(2+c)}{3} \\
H_s &= \frac{c\omega}{3} \frac{2c\omega(1-c)}{(1-c)(1-\omega)} = \frac{2c^2\omega^2}{3(1-\omega)} = F_s \frac{2c\omega(1-c)}{3}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we can take the first derivative with respect to $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-SP}^*}{\partial \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}} &= -2E_s F_s^2 \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} + G_s + 2H_s \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \\
&= (-2E_s F_s^2 + 2H_s) \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} + G_s \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

This is positive as both terms are positive,

$$G_s = \frac{c\omega(2+c)}{3} \geq 0$$

and

$$-2E_s F_s^2 + 2H_s = 2F_s \left(-\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{3} \frac{c\omega}{(1-c)(1-\omega)} + \frac{2c\omega(1-c)}{3} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 2F_s \frac{c\omega(1-c)}{3} (-1+2) \\
&= \frac{2}{3} \frac{c^2\omega^2}{(1-\omega)} \geq 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*$ is monotonically increasing in $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$.

Consequently, minimum/maximum profits for $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^{\min} = 0$ and $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^{\max} = \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2c\omega}$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = 0; B_s = 0) &= \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{3} - c\omega \\
\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*\left(\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2c\omega}; B_s = \frac{1}{2}\right) &= \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{4} - c\omega + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)}{2} \\
&= \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)(3-c)}{4} - c\omega
\end{aligned}$$

and, thus,

$$\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{3} - c\omega \leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(p_s^*) \leq \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)(3-c)}{4} - c\omega. \quad (86)$$

3) Third, we consider $2/3 < 2(1+B_s)/3 \leq \lambda \leq 1 \wedge B_s \leq 1/2$ and rearrange

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP}^* &= (1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda \left(-\frac{B_s^2}{3\lambda-2} + \frac{1}{2} \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \left(c + \frac{2\lambda B_s(1-c)}{3\lambda-2} \right) \right) \\
0 &\leq \frac{B_s}{3\lambda-2} \leq \frac{1}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^* = (1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda \left(-I_s B_s + \frac{1}{2} \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(c + 2I_s \lambda(1-c)) \right)$$

with

$$I_s = \frac{B_s}{3\lambda-2}$$

and as

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{2}{3} &\leq \frac{2(1+B_s)}{3} \leq \lambda \leq 1 \\
0 &\leq 2B_s \leq 3\lambda-2 \leq 1 \\
0 &\leq I_s \leq \frac{1}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

We rearrange further,

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP}^* &= -\lambda I_s c \omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} (1-c) + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} - c \omega + c \omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} (c + 2I_s \lambda (1-c)) \\
&= c \omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} (-\lambda I_s (1-c) + c + 2I_s \lambda (1-c)) + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} - c \omega \\
&= c \omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} (\lambda I_s (1-c) + c) + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} - c \omega.
\end{aligned}$$

Again, this is linearly increasing in $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$. Thus, minimum/maximum profits for $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^{\min} = 0$

and $\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^{\max} = \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2c\omega}$ and $I_s^{\min} = 0$ and $I_s^{\max} = 1/2$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*(\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = 0; I_s = 0) &= \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} - c \omega \\
\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*\left(\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} = \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2c\omega}; I_s = \frac{1}{2}\right) \\
&= \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda}{2}(1-c) + c\right) + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} - c \omega \\
&= \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{3}{2}\lambda(1-c) + c\right) - c \omega.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, profits range in

$$\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \lambda}{2} - c \omega \leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^* \leq \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{3}{2}\lambda(1-c) + c\right) - c \omega.$$

Furthermore, we examine $\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*$ with respect to λ

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \pi_{PAYW-SP}^*}{\partial \lambda} &= \frac{c \omega \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} B_s (-2)}{(3\lambda - 2)^2} + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{2} \\
&= \frac{c^2 \omega^2 \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^2}{(1-\omega)} \left(-\frac{2}{(3\lambda - 2)^2} + \frac{(1-\omega)^2 (1-c)^2}{2c^2 \omega^2 \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^2} \right) \\
&= \frac{2c^2 \omega^2 \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}^2}{(1-\omega)} \left(-\frac{1}{(3\lambda - 2)^2} + \frac{1}{4B_s} \right) \geq 0
\end{aligned}$$

as $\frac{2(1+B_s)}{3} \leq \lambda$.

The minimum and maximum λ values are given by $\lambda = \frac{2}{3}$ and $\lambda = 1$ as we are in case of $2/3 < 2(1+B_s)/3 \leq \lambda \leq 1 \wedge B_s \leq 1/2$. Therefore, use these values in the profit range determined before,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} - c\omega &\leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^* & (87) \\ &\leq \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2} \left(\frac{3}{2}\lambda(1-c) + c \right) - c\omega. & (AW.A.16) \end{aligned}$$

For $\lambda = \frac{2}{3}$

$$\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{3} - c\omega \leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^* \leq \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)}{2} - c\omega \quad (88)$$

and for $\lambda = 1$

$$\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{2} - c\omega \leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^* \leq \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)(3-c)}{4} - c\omega. \quad (89)$$

(AW.A.16)

Thus, overall, the profits in PAYW-SP span

$$\frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2}{3} - c\omega \leq \pi_{PAYW-SP}^* \leq \frac{(1-c)(1-\omega)(3-c)}{4} - c\omega.$$

Note that this corresponds to (86).

5 Derivations of Proposition 4 (Comparisons between the pricing mechanisms)

5.1 Setup

In their calculation of optimal pricing regimes, CKZ use equations (7), (39), (61), and (63) to calculate the regions in which each pricing regime PAAP, PAYW-MP, PAYW-SP optimal. As they build on their previous results, their outcomes differ from our outcome because they

- (a) disregard the screening out of freeloaders in PAYW-SP (cf. Section 4),
- (b) abstract from disadvantageous inequity aversion (cf. Sections 2.1 and 3)

Furthermore, in their calculations of optimal pricing regions, three additional errata occur.

CKZ

- (c) make calculating errors when deriving the optimal profit difference between PAYW-MP and PAYW-SP when $\lambda \leq \frac{2}{3}$,
- (d) do not account for the upper bound of the minimum price in their profit comparisons, and
- (e) leave an area undefined regarding the definition of the optimal pricing scheme.

To unveil these inconsistencies, we first retrace their calculations by using their profit functions and to derive consistent optimal pricing schemes. Note, these results still suffer from (a) and (b) above but should not be affected by (c), (d) and (e). Second, we compare these consistent schemes to CKZ's results and try to uncover and interpret the differences. Third, we use CKZ's optimal minimum and suggested prices to derive the profits a seller would make with inconsistent prices. These prices are later used in our simulation analysis. Fourth and finally, we derive the optimal pricing schemes using the correct prices and correct profit functions.

5.2 Profit comparisons for CKZ's results

CKZ compare their profits in Proposition 4. However, the calculations are performed in the proofs in their Appendix D. They use their respective profit functions which we derived in (7), (39), (61), and (63).

5.2.1 Comparing pricing schemes for $\lambda \geq 2/3$

First, CKZ compare optimal profits for $\lambda \geq \frac{2}{3}$. We follow their reasoning and start by comparing the optimal profits for PAYW-MP to the optimal profits under PAYW-SP

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ,*} &= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda [1 - 2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda]}{2(1 - \theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda)} - \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} (1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1-c)^2 - c\theta \right) \\ &= \frac{\theta^{CKZ} (\theta^{CKZ} \lambda + c^2 \theta^{CKZ} \lambda + c(-2 - 2\theta^{CKZ}(-1 + \lambda) + 4\lambda))}{2(-1 + \theta^{CKZ} + 2\lambda)} \\ &= \frac{\theta^{CKZ} [\lambda[4c + \theta^{CKZ}(1-c)^2] - 2c(1 - \theta^{CKZ})]}{2(-1 + \theta^{CKZ} + 2\lambda)}. \end{aligned}$$

To check the sign of the above expression, we start by inspecting whether the sign of the denominator is positive,

$$\begin{aligned} 2(-1 + \theta^{CKZ} + 2\lambda) &> 0 \\ (-1 + \theta^{CKZ} + 2\lambda) &> 0 \\ 2\lambda &> 1 - \theta^{CKZ}. \end{aligned}$$

As $\lambda > \frac{2}{3}$ and $0 \leq \theta^{CKZ} \leq 1$, this is always the case. The denominator is always positive.

Second, we test the nominator

$$\theta^{CKZ} [\lambda[4c + \theta^{CKZ}(1-c)^2] - 2c(1 - \theta^{CKZ})] > 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda[4c + \theta^{CKZ}(1-c)^2] - 2c(1 - \theta^{CKZ}) &> 0 \\
\lambda[4c + \theta^{CKZ}(1-c)^2] &> 2c(1 - \theta^{CKZ}) \\
4c + (1-c)^2\theta^{CKZ} &> \frac{2c - 2c\theta^{CKZ}}{\lambda} \\
\theta^{CKZ} \left((1-c)^2 + \frac{2c}{\lambda} \right) &> -4c + \frac{2c}{\lambda} \\
\theta^{CKZ} &> \frac{c(2-4\lambda)}{2c + (1-c)^2\lambda} < 0.
\end{aligned}$$

The nominator is also positive. Thus, the whole expression $\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ,*}$ is always positive. Therefore, PAYW-MP is always better than PAYW-SP when $\lambda > \frac{2}{3}$.

Next, we compare PAYW-MP to PAAP,

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAAP}^{\beta=0,*} &= \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda[1 - 2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda]}{2(1 - \theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda)} - \frac{(1-c)^2}{4} \\
&= \frac{(1-c)^2(1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - 2\lambda)^2}{4(-1 + \theta^{CKZ} + 2\lambda)}.
\end{aligned}$$

To inspect whether PAAP can dominate PAYW-MP in this case, thus, whether this difference can become negative, we first inspect the denominator

$$\begin{aligned}
4(-1 + \theta^{CKZ} + 2\lambda) &> 0 \\
(-1 + \theta^{CKZ} + 2\lambda) &> 0 \\
2\lambda &> 1 - \theta^{CKZ}.
\end{aligned}$$

As before, the denominator is always positive for $\lambda > \frac{1}{2}$. As $\lambda > \frac{2}{3}$ this is the case. Next, we move to the nominator.

$$(1-c)^2(1 - \theta^{CKZ})(1 - 2\lambda)^2 > 0.$$

This is always positive as $\theta^{CKZ} \leq 1$. Thus, $\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAAP}^{\beta=0,*}$ is positive and PAYW-MP is always better than PAAP when $\lambda > \frac{2}{3}$. This result corresponds to CKZ.

5.2.2 Comparing pricing schemes for $1/2 \leq \lambda < 2/3$

Next, we consider $\frac{1}{2} \leq \lambda < \frac{2}{3}$. First, we compare PAYW-MP to PAAP,

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAAP}^{\beta=0,*}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda [1 - 2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda]}{2(1-\theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda)} - \left(-c\theta^{CKZ} + \frac{[2+z(3\lambda-2)](1-c)^2(1-\theta^{CKZ})}{6} \right) \\
&= c\theta^{CKZ} + \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda [1 - 2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda]}{2(1-\theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda)} - \frac{[2+z(3\lambda-2)](1-c)^2(1-\theta^{CKZ})}{6}.
\end{aligned}$$

CKZ solve this term for θ^{CKZ} to find the critical threshold of “freeloaders” for which PAYW-MP is better than PAYW-SP. To compare, we do the same and solve $\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAAP}^{\beta=0,*}$ for θ^{CKZ} . This gives us

$$\theta_{RE,1,2}^{CKZ} = \frac{A_{RE}^{CKZ} \pm \sqrt{B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ}}}{D_{RE}^{CKZ}}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{RE}^{CKZ} &= 2 - 2z + c(-1 - 2c(-1+z) + 4z) - 5\lambda + ((4-5c)c + 5(1-c)^2z)\lambda \\
&\quad + 3(1-c)^2(1-z)\lambda^2 \\
&= 2 - c(1 - 2c(1-z) - 4z) - 2z - 5\lambda + ((4-5c)c + 5(-1+c)^2z)\lambda \\
&\quad + 3(1-c)^2(1-z)\lambda^2
\end{aligned} \tag{90}$$

$$B_{RE}^{CKZ} = 3c^2 + 2(-1 + c(2 + c(-4+z) - 2z) + z)\lambda + 3(1-c)^2(1-z)\lambda^2$$

$$C_{RE}^{CKZ} = 3 + 2(-4 + (-2+c)c(-1+z) + z)\lambda - 3(-1+c)^2(-1+z)\lambda^2$$

$$D_{RE}^{CKZ} = 2(1+c+c^2-z(1-c)^2) + 3z\lambda(1-c)^2.$$

Note, CKZ derive similar results and denote their auxiliary variables A, B, C, D . Therefore, we exceptionally also use C with a capital letter as an auxiliary variable in this context.

First, check the feasibility of both solutions $\theta_{RE,1}^{CKZ}$ and $\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ}$.

We check whether the denominator D_{RE}^{CKZ} can become negative

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{RE}^{CKZ} &< 0 \\
2(1+c+c^2-z(1-c)^2) + 3z\lambda(1-c)^2 &< 0.
\end{aligned}$$

The second term, $3z\lambda(1-c)^2$, is always positive. Therefore, we only inspect the first term

$$\begin{aligned}
2(1+c+c^2-z(1-c)^2) &< 0 \\
2(1-z+c+c^2(1-z)+2cz) &< 0 \\
1+c+c^2(1-z)+2cz &< z.
\end{aligned}$$

A contradiction as $z \in [0; 1]$ can never become larger than 1. Thus, the denominator, D_{RE}^{CKZ} , is always positive.

Second, we inspect the nominator for the first solution

$$\theta_{RE,1}^{CKZ} = \frac{A_{RE}^{CKZ} - \sqrt{B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ}}}{D_{RE}^{CKZ}}.$$

For a viable solution in $\theta_{RE,1}^{CKZ}$, we need numerator to be positive as well. Thus,

$$A_{RE}^{CKZ} - \sqrt{B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ}} > 0$$

$$A_{RE}^{CKZ} > \sqrt{B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ}}$$

$$A_{RE}^{CKZ^2} > B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &> (2 - 2z + c(-1 - 2c(-1 + z) + 4z) - 5\lambda + ((4 - 5c)c + 5(-1 + c)^2 z)\lambda \\ &\quad - 3(-1 + c)^2(-1 + z)\lambda^2)^2 - (3c^2 + 2(-1 + c(2 + c(-4 + z) - 2z) + z)\lambda \\ &\quad - 3(-1 + c)^2(-1 + z)\lambda^2)(3 + 2(-4 + (-2 + c)c(-1 + z) + z)\lambda \\ &\quad - 3(-1 + c)^2(-1 + z)\lambda^2). \end{aligned}$$

However, this is not the case as

$$\begin{aligned} &(2 - 2z + c(-1 - 2c(-1 + z) + 4z) - 5\lambda + ((4 - 5c)c + 5(-1 + c)^2 z)\lambda \\ &\quad - 3(-1 + c)^2(-1 + z)\lambda^2)^2 - (3c^2 + 2(-1 + c(2 + c(-4 + z) - 2z) + z)\lambda \\ &\quad - 3(-1 + c)^2(-1 + z)\lambda^2)(3 + 2(-4 + (-2 + c)c(-1 + z) + z)\lambda \\ &\quad - 3(-1 + c)^2(-1 + z)\lambda^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$= \underbrace{(1-c)^2}_{>0} \underbrace{(1-z)}_{>0} \underbrace{(2-7\lambda+6\lambda^2)}_{<0} \left(\underbrace{2+z(-2+3\lambda)}_{>-\frac{1}{2}} + \underbrace{c(2+z(4-6\lambda))}_{>0} + c^2 \left(\underbrace{2+z(-2+3\lambda)}_{>-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right)$$

$$\leq 0.$$

Thus, the nominator is always smaller 0 and, therefore, θ_1 does not yield a meaningful solution. Second, we test whether

$$\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ} = \frac{A_{RE}^{CKZ} + \sqrt{B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ}}}{D_{RE}^{CKZ}}$$

yields a meaningful solution. Therefore, we consider $\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ}$ to be a function of λ, z and c and inspect the boundaries to test $(\exists \lambda, c, z) \theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ}(\lambda, c, z) \in [0, 1]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ}(\lambda, c, z) &= \\
\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ}\left(\frac{1}{2}, c, z\right) &= \frac{-1 + (-2 + c)c(-1 + z) - \sqrt{(1 - c)^4(1 - z)^2 + z}}{-8(1 + c + c^2) + 2(1 - c)^2z} \\
&= \frac{-1 + (-2 + c)c(-1 + z) - (1 - c)^2(1 - z) + z}{-8(1 + c + c^2) + 2(1 - c)^2z} \\
&= \frac{(1 - c)^2(1 - z)}{4(1 + c + c^2) - (1 - c)^2z}.
\end{aligned}$$

We see that the nominator

$$1 > (1 - c)^2(1 - z) \geq 0,$$

as $1 > c, z \geq 0$.

For the denominator we find,

$$4(1 + c + c^2) - (1 - c)^2z > 0.$$

Thus, for $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$, $0 \leq \theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ} < 1$.

We also inspect the upper boundary,

$$\begin{aligned}
\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ}\left(\frac{2}{3}, c, z\right) &= \frac{-c + \sqrt{c^2}}{2(1 + c + c^2)} \\
&= 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ}$ is a viable solution. Hence, PAYW-MP and PAYW-SP are possible for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \lambda < \frac{2}{3}$. Therefore, we define

$$\theta_{RE,2}^{CKZ} := \theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+} \quad (91)$$

as the critical threshold indicating whether PAYW-MP or PAYW-SP are optimal. As shown in the previous chapter PAYW-MP is always better than PAAP for $\lambda > \frac{1}{2}$. Therefore, a comparison between PAYW-SP and PAAP is redundant.

5.2.3 Comparing pricing schemes for $\lambda < 1/2$

First, we compare PAAP to PAYW-MP

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAAP}^* = (1 - c)^2(1 - \lambda)\lambda - \frac{(1 - c)^2}{4}$$

$$= (1 - c)^2 \left((1 - \lambda)\lambda - \frac{1}{4} \right).$$

We only need to consider the second term

$$(1 - \lambda)\lambda - \frac{1}{4} < 0$$

$$(1 - \lambda)\lambda < \frac{1}{4}.$$

This is true, because $\lambda < 1/2$. Thus, PAAP is always preferred to PAYW-MP in this interval.

Therefore, comparing PAYW-MP to PAYW-SP would be redundant.

Consequently, we only need to compare PAYW-SP to PAAP.

$$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAAP}^* = 1/6 (1 - c)^2 (1 - \theta^{CKZ}) (2 + z(-2 + 3\lambda)) - c\theta^{CKZ} - \frac{(1 - c)^2}{4}.$$

To find the critical level of freeloaders, we set to zero and solve for θ^{CKZ} . This gives us

$$\theta^{CKZ} \leq \frac{(1 - c)^2 (1 + z(-4 + 6\lambda))}{4(1 + c + c^2 - (1 - c)^2 z) + 6(-1 + c)^2 z\lambda} := \theta_{RE, \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}}^{CKZ,+} \quad (92)$$

Thus, we can conclude:

- For $\lambda \geq 2/3$, PAYW-MP is optimal.
- For $\frac{1}{2} < \lambda < 2/3$,
 - PAYW-MP is optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} \geq \theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+}$ and
 - PAYW-SP is optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} < \theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+}$
- For $\lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}$
 - PAAP is optimal if $\theta_{RE, \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}}^{CKZ,+}$ and
 - PAYW-SP is optimal if $\theta_{RE, \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}}^{CKZ,+}$.

Figure 1 describes the results graphically.

Figure 1: Optimal pricing schemes when using CKZ's profit functions

5.3 CKZ's results

The above calculations use CKZ's optimal prices and the resulting optimal profit functions. These functions do not take less fair-minded consumers or disadvantageous inequity aversion into account and therefore draw a misleading picture. However, our results above are different than the solution of CKZ in their Proposition 4 and in the corresponding proofs. In the following, we are going to compare our results to those of CKZ. As the process of calculation in the original paper is not always transparent, we only speculate about the reasons for deviation.

In their Proposition 4, CKZ's recommendations for the firm's pricing choice are:

- For $\lambda > 2/3$, PAYW-MP is optimal.
- For $\lambda \leq 2/3$, CKZ define
 - PAYW-MP to be optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} > \max\{1 - 2\lambda, \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)\}$
 - PAYW-SP to be optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} \leq \min\{\theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda), E_{ORIG}^{CKZ}\}$ and
 - PAAP to be optimal if $E_{ORIG}^{CKZ} \leq \theta^{CKZ} \leq \min\{1 - 2\lambda, \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)\}$,

with

$$\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda) = \frac{A_{ORIG}^{CKZ} + \sqrt{B_{ORIG}^{CKZ} C_{ORIG}^{CKZ}}}{D_{ORIG}^{CKZ}} \quad (93)$$

$$A_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = 2 - 2z - c[1 - 2c(1 - z)] - 4z - 5\lambda - \lambda(c(4 - 5c) + 5z(1 - c)^2) + 3\lambda(1 - z)(1 - c)^2$$

$$B_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = 3c^2 - 2\lambda(1 - z - c(2 - 2z - c(4 - z))) + 3\lambda 2(1 - c)2(1 - z) = 3c^2 + 12(1 - c)(1 - z)\lambda - 2(1 - c(2 - c(4 - z) - 2z) - z)\lambda$$

$$C_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = 3 - 2\lambda(4 - z - c(2 - c)(1 - z)) + 3\lambda 2(1 - c)2(1 - z) = 3 + 12(1 - c)(1 - z)\lambda - 2(4 - (2 - c)c(1 - z) - z)\lambda$$

$$D_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = 2(1 + c + c^2 - (1 - c)^2 z) + 3(1 - c)^2 z \lambda$$

$$E_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = \frac{(1 - c)^2 (1 - z(4 - 6\lambda))}{4(1 + c + c^2 - (1 - c)^2 z) + 6(1 - c)^2 z \lambda}.$$

Our results partially differ from CKZ's. While we also find that PAYW-MP should be optimal for $\lambda \geq 2/3$, we find a different structure for value for $\lambda \leq 2/3$. In particular, we do not find $\theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$ and the boundary $1 - 2\lambda$. However, their lower boundary for PAAP to be more profitable than PAYW, E , is equal to our boundary $\theta_{RE, \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}}^{CKZ,+}$.

In the following subsections, we first try to disentangle how and why the critical thresholds of “freeloaders” differ between our results in Section 5.2 and the results by CKZ. Second, we will discuss the different boundaries in Section 5.2 and CKZ.

5.3.1 Differences in θ^+

When we inspect $\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$, we find a similar mathematical structure for the results derived in Section 5.2

$$\theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+} = \frac{A_{RE}^{CKZ} + \sqrt{B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ}}}{D_{RE}^{CKZ}}$$

and CKZ's results

$$\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+} = \frac{A_{ORIG}^{CKZ} + \sqrt{B_{ORIG}^{CKZ} C_{ORIG}^{CKZ}}}{D_{ORIG}^{CKZ}}.$$

However, the boundaries are different,

$$\theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+} \neq \theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}.$$

This similarity allows us to compare A_{RE}^{CKZ} to A_{ORIG}^{CKZ} , B_{RE}^{CKZ} to B_{ORIG}^{CKZ} , C_{RE}^{CKZ} to C_{ORIG}^{CKZ} and D_{RE}^{CKZ} to D_{ORIG}^{CKZ} . However, only the denominator is equivalent in both equations.

$$D_{RE}^{CKZ} = D_{ORIG}^{CKZ}$$

$$2(1 + c + c^2 - z(1 - c)^2) + 3z\lambda(1 - c)^2 = 2(1 + c + c^2 - (1 - c)^2 z) + 3(1 - c)^2 z \lambda.$$

This is surprising since we use the same starting point as CKZ in their Proposition 4. We test several potential explanations for this difference.

5.3.1.1 Potential explanation: Calculation mistake

A potential reason for the difference between $\theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+}$ and $\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$ is a calculation mistake or typo in the comparison between the profits of PAYW-MP and PAYW-SP for $\lambda \leq \frac{2}{3}$ in the Proof to Proposition 4 in CKZ which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ,*} &= c\theta^{CKZ} + \frac{(2+z(3\lambda-2))(1-c)^2(1-\theta^{CKZ})}{6} \\ &+ \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda[1-2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda)-2\lambda]}{2(1-\theta^{CKZ}-2\lambda)}. \end{aligned} \quad (94)$$

However, using their optimal profits, the “revenue part” of PAYW-SP ($\frac{(2+z(3\lambda-2))(1-c)^2(1-\theta^{CKZ})}{6}$) should be subtracted from (instead of added to) the profits in PAYW-MP

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} - \pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ,*} &= c\theta^{CKZ} - \frac{(2+z(3\lambda-2))(1-c)^2(1-\theta^{CKZ})}{6} \\ &+ \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda[1-2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda)-2\lambda]}{2(1-\theta^{CKZ}-2\lambda)}. \end{aligned}$$

In order to check whether this is the cause for the difference between (92) and (93), we use (94) set it to zero and solve for θ^{CKZ} . However, we find

$$\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+'} = \frac{A_{ORIG}^{CKZ,'} \pm \sqrt{B_{ORIG}^{CKZ,'}}}{D_{ORIG}^{CKZ,'}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_{ORIG}^{CKZ,'} &= 2(-2+c(7+2c(-1+z)-4z)+2z-\lambda-(c(4+c)+5(-1+c)^2z)\lambda \\ &+ 3(-1+c)^2(1+z)\lambda^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_{ORIG}^{CKZ,'} &= 4\left((2-2z+c(-7-2c(-1+z)+4z)+\lambda+(c(4+c)+5(-1+c)^2z)\lambda \right. \\ &- 3(-1+c)^2(1+z)\lambda^2)^2 \\ &+ (-1+c)^2(-1+2\lambda)(2-2z+2c(-5+c+2z-cz)+3(-1+c)^2z\lambda)(2 \\ &+ 3\lambda+z(-2+3\lambda)) \end{aligned}$$

$$D_{ORIG}^{CKZ,'} = -4(1+(-5+c)c)+4(-1+c)^2z-6(-1+c)^2z\lambda.$$

This does not correspond to $\theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+}$ or its components (A_{RE}^{CKZ} , B_{RE}^{CKZ} , C_{RE}^{CKZ} , and D_{RE}^{CKZ}).

Therefore, we suspect that the erroneous minus sign was a typo in CKZ’s Proof to Proposition 4 and did not bias the calculation of $\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}$.

5.3.1.2 Potential explanation: Missing superscripts

A close inspection of B_{ORIG}^{CKZ} and C_{ORIG}^{CKZ} suggest that there might be a simple typographic or formatting error in CKZ's paper.

$$B_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = 3c^2 - 2\lambda \left(1 - z - c(2 - 2z - c(4 - z)) \right) + 3\lambda 2(1 - c)2(1 - z)$$

$$C_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = 3 - 2\lambda(4 - z - c(2 - c)(1 - z)) + 3\lambda 2(1 - c)2(1 - z)$$

The second term of both equations

$$"3\lambda 2(1 - c)2(1 - z)"$$

exhibits an unusual pattern of three integers that could be multiplied and displayed as a single number. As two of these numbers are 2's, we suspect that these are supposed to be (quadratic) superscripts. Thus, we compare our results with these updated values $B_{ORIG}^{CKZ'}$ and $C_{ORIG}^{CKZ'}$.

$$B_{ORIG}^{CKZ''} = 3c^2 - 2\lambda \left(1 - z - c(2 - 2z - c(4 - z)) \right) + 3\lambda^2(1 - c)^2(1 - z)$$

$$= 3c^2 - 2(1 - c(2 - c(4 - z) - 2z) - z)\lambda + 3(1 - c)^2(1 - z)\lambda^2$$

$$C_{ORIG}^{CKZ''} = 3 - 2\lambda(4 - z - c(2 - c)(1 - z)) + 3\lambda^2(1 - c)^2(1 - z)$$

$$= 3 - 2(4 - (2 - c)c(1 - z) - z)\lambda + 3(1 - c)^2(1 - z)\lambda^2.$$

If we compare the product of $B_{ORIG}^{CKZ''}$ and $C_{ORIG}^{CKZ''}$ to the counterpart in our solution, the product of B_{RE}^{CKZ} and C_{RE}^{CKZ} , we find equivalence:

$$B_{RE}^{CKZ} C_{RE}^{CKZ} = B_{ORIG}^{CKZ''} C_{ORIG}^{CKZ''}.$$

Thus, the deviation between B_{RE}^{CKZ} and B_{ORIG}^{CKZ} and C_{RE}^{CKZ} to C_{ORIG}^{CKZ} is probably due to a formatting error.

However, we still find no equivalence with respect to A_{RE}^{CKZ} and A_{ORIG}^{CKZ} .

$$A_{RE}^{CKZ} - A_{ORIG}^{CKZ} = (2 - 2z - c[1 - 2c(1 - z)] - 4z - 5\lambda - \lambda(c(4 - 5c) + 5z(1 - c)^2)$$

$$+ 3\lambda(1 - z)(1 - c)^2)$$

$$- (2 - c(1 - 2c(1 - z) - 4z) - 2z - 5\lambda + ((4 - 5c)c + 5(-1 + c)^2z)\lambda$$

$$+ 3(1 - c)^2(1 - z)\lambda^2)$$

$$= -4(1 + c)z + (3 - 14c + 13c^2 - 13(-1 + c)^2z)\lambda$$

$$+ 3(-1 + c)^2(-1 + z)\lambda^2$$

$$\neq 0.$$

Unfortunately, we could not discover the cause for this difference. Therefore, the reason for

$\theta_{RE, \frac{1}{2} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}}^{CKZ,+} \neq \theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}$ remains unclear.

5.3.1.3 Potential explanation: Wrong $\pi_{PAYW-MP}$ for $\lambda < 1/2$

In their comparison of boundaries for $\lambda < 1/2$, CKZ compare PAYW-MP to PAAP and PAYW-SP. However, they do not use the right minimum price for optimal profits. As shown in (39), profits in PAYW with the minimum price are given by

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP,1}^{\beta=0*} = \begin{cases} (1-c)^2 \lambda (1-\lambda) & \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda (2\lambda + 2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda) - 1)}{2(2\lambda + \theta^{CKZ} - 1)} & \lambda > \frac{1}{2} \end{cases}$$

However, in their comparison between PAYW-MP and PAYW-SP as well as PAYW-MP and PAAP for $\lambda < 2/3$, CKZ use

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ,*} = \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda [1 - 2\theta^{CKZ}(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda]}{2(1 - \theta^{CKZ} - 2\lambda)}$$

Using the correct form (37) and comparing PAYW-MP to PAAP would give

$$\pi_{PAYW-MP,1}^{\beta=0*} - \pi_{PAAP}^* = (1-c)^2 \lambda (1-\lambda) - \frac{(1-c)^2}{4} < 0.$$

Thus, PAAP is always greater than PAYW-MP for $\lambda < 1/2$. Therefore, CKZ's boundaries $\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}$ should not be considered for $\lambda < 1/2$.

5.3.2 Different boundaries

In addition to the previous errors, CKZ's formulation of boundaries is inconsequential for $\lambda \leq 2/3$. As noted above, they assume

- PAYW-MP to be optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} > \max\{1 - 2\lambda, \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)\}$
- PAYW-SP to be optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} \leq \min\{\theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda), E_{ORIG}^{CKZ}\}$ and
- PAAP to be optimal if $E_{ORIG}^{CKZ} \leq \theta^{CKZ} \leq \min\{1 - 2\lambda, \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)\}$,

This implies that $1 - 2\lambda \geq \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$ and $1 - 2\lambda \leq \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$ can be the case.

Furthermore, $\theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda) \geq E_{ORIG}^{CKZ}$ or $\theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda) \leq E$.

Imagine the following scenario, $\theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda) \geq E_{ORIG}^{CKZ}$, $1 - 2\lambda \leq \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$.

Furthermore, we assume $1 - 2\lambda \geq E_{ORIG}^{CKZ}$. In this case, they predict that

- PAYW-MP is optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} > \theta^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$
- PAYW-SP is optimal if $\theta^{CKZ} \leq E_{ORIG}^{CKZ}$ and
- PAAP is optimal if $E_{ORIG}^{CKZ} \leq \theta^{CKZ} \leq 1 - 2\lambda$.

Consequently, in the area between $1 - 2\lambda$ and $\theta^+(z, c, \lambda)$ the optimal pricing scheme is undefined. This problem prevails for other relations between the boundaries. Consider Figure 2 for an overview of all possible combinations. Note the blank areas where optimal pricing is undefined.

Figure 2: CKZ's boundary formulation

5.4 CKZ's prices and AW profit functions

In the simulation in Section 6.3 in the paper, we offer a comparison between our profits and CKZ's profits. However, as shown above, CKZ's formulation is inconsistent. However, to estimate the magnitude of their misspecification, we calculate CKZ's profits with the "correct" but not optimal profit functions and use the prices derived by CKZ. PAYW and PAAP prices do not need to be recalculated as the seller does not set a price in PAYW and as the PAAP price was calculated correctly by CKZ.

5.4.1 Profits for PAYW-MP

We use (48) as profit function and insert CKZ's optimal price (36). This gives us

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-MP}(\underline{p}^{CKZ,*}) & \tag{95} \\
&= \frac{1}{2\lambda(1+\beta\lambda)} \left(\left(2c\lambda(1+\beta\lambda)(\lambda(-1+\omega) - \omega) \right. \right. \\
&\quad - \lambda^2(1+\beta\lambda)(-1+\omega) \\
&\quad + c^2(-1+\lambda)(-1+\omega + \lambda(1-\omega + \beta(1+\lambda+\omega - \lambda\omega))) \\
&\quad + \max\left(c, \min\left(c + \lambda - c\lambda, c - \frac{(-1+c)\lambda\omega}{-1+2\lambda+\omega}\right)\right) \left(2c(-1 \right. \\
&\quad + (2+\beta)\lambda) - 2(c(-1+\lambda) - \lambda)(1+\beta\lambda)\omega \\
&\quad - (-1+\omega \\
&\quad + \lambda(2+\beta \\
&\quad + \beta\omega)) \max\left(c, \min\left(c + \lambda - c\lambda, c - \frac{(-1+c)\lambda\omega}{-1+2\lambda+\omega}\right)\right) \left. \right) \left. \right) \\
&:= \pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZnew,*}.
\end{aligned}$$

5.4.2 Profits for PAYW-SP

We use (67) and (76) as profit functions. Optimal prices are given by (64). This leads us to the following profit function

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi_{PAYW-SP}(p_s^{CKZ,*}) & \tag{96} \\
&= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{6}(-1+c)^2(2+z(-2+3\lambda)) + \frac{1}{6}\omega(-3(1-c)^2z\lambda) + \\ \frac{1}{3}\omega\left(-1+z+c\left(-1+2\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} - 2z(1+\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}) + c(-1+z+\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]} + 2z\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]})\right)\right) & \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \\ \frac{1}{2}(-(1-c)^2\lambda(-1+\omega) + 2c(-1+c\gamma)\omega) & \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \end{cases} \\
&:= \pi_{PAYW-SP}^{CKZnew,*}.
\end{aligned}$$

Note: $\frac{2+c}{3} > p_h$ for $\lambda < 2/3$

5.5 Finding the optimal pricing scheme

In this section we offer the optimal pricing scheme choice using our optimal prices and the correct formulation of the profit function. We analyze analytically under which conditions the difference between two profit functions $\pi_1 - \pi_2$ is positive / negative which implies that policy 1 is preferred over policy 2 or vice versa.

5.5.1 Comparing PAAP to PAYW-MP

First, we want to consider the circumstances for which PAAP is chosen over PAYW-MP.

$$\pi_{PAAP}^* - \pi_{PAYW-MP}^* > 0.$$

As previously discussed, the optimal profits under PAYW-MP are given by a piecewise function:

$$\frac{(1-c)^2(1+\lambda\beta)}{4(1+\beta)} - \begin{cases} \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda(1-\lambda)}{1+\beta\lambda} & \lambda \leq 1/(2+\beta) \\ \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda(2+\beta) + 2\omega(1-\lambda) - 1}{(2+\beta(1+\omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega} \right) & \lambda > 1/(2+\beta) \end{cases} > 0.$$

First, we consider $\lambda \leq 1/(2+\beta)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAAP}^* - \pi_{PAYW-MP,1}^* &= \frac{(1-c)^2(1+\lambda\beta)}{4(1+\beta)} - \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda(1-\lambda)}{1+\beta\lambda} \\ &= \frac{(1-c)^2(1-(2+\beta)\lambda)^2}{4(1+\beta)(1+\beta\lambda)}. \end{aligned}$$

We inspect the nominator,

$$(1-c)^2(1-(2+\beta)\lambda)^2 \geq 0$$

This is always positive. Second, we move to the denominator,

$$4(1+\beta)(1+\beta\lambda) > 0.$$

Thus, the term is always positive. Hence, PAAP is always better for $\lambda \leq 1/(2+\beta)$.

Next, we consider the $\lambda > 1/(2+\beta)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{PAAP}^* - \pi_{PAYW-MP,2}^* &= \frac{(1-c)^2(1+\lambda\beta)}{4(1+\beta)} - \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda(2+\beta) + 2\omega(1-\lambda) - 1}{(2+\beta(1+\omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega} \right) \\ &= \frac{-(1-c)^2(1-\lambda(2+\beta))^2(1-\omega)}{4(1+\beta)(1-\omega-\lambda(2+\beta+\beta\omega))}. \end{aligned}$$

The nominator,

$$(1-c)^2(1-\lambda(2+\beta))^2(1-\omega) \geq 0,$$

is always positive as $0 \leq \omega \leq 1$.

Next, we move to the denominator,

$$(2 + \beta(1 + \omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega \geq (2 + \beta)\lambda - 1 + \omega > 1 - 1 + \omega \geq 1.$$

Therefore, the whole expression is negative. Thus, PAYW-MP is always better for $\lambda > 1/(2 + \beta)$.

Next, we derive the critical λ^+ where profits from PAAP and PAYW-MP equal PAYW-SP.

Due to the prominent role of generosity λ , we determine the critical threshold λ^+ for which $\pi_1(\lambda^+) = \pi_2(\lambda^+)$; this implies that for $\lambda < \lambda^+$ policy 1 dominates policy 2 and vice versa

for $\lambda > \lambda^+$. Since the comparison between profit functions apply in each case to a certain domain of λ (small, intermediate, large), the respective domain is also effective for λ^+ .

However, only for small λ , $\lambda^+ \notin [0; 1/(2 + \beta)]$ might occur. This stands in contrast to CKZ who derive the optimal pricing scheme based on the critical threshold $\theta^{CKZ,+}$.

5.5.2 Comparing PAAP to PAYW-SP

We compare PAAP to PAYW-SP (for $B_s > 1/2$ and $B_s \leq 1/2$) and solve for λ . Thus, we first collect terms for a more compact computation,

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAAP}^* &= \frac{(1 - c)^2(1 + \beta\lambda)}{4(1 + \beta)} \\ &= A_{AW} + \beta\lambda A_{AW}\end{aligned}$$

with

$$A_{AW} = \frac{(1 - c)^2}{4(1 + \beta)}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW-SP}^* &= (1 - \omega)(1 - c)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda z}{2} + g_{1\lambda}(1 - z) \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + g_{2\lambda}(1 - z)) \right) \\ &= B_{AW}\lambda - B_{AW}\lambda\omega + D_{AW} - \omega D_{AW} - c\omega E_{AW}\end{aligned}$$

with $B_{AW} = \frac{(1-c)^2 z}{2}$, $D_{AW} = (1 - c)^2(1 - z)g_{1\lambda}$, $E_{AW} = \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + g_{2\lambda}(1 - z)) \right)$.

We compare the profit functions,

$$\pi_{PAYW}^* = \pi_{PAYW-SP}^*$$

$$A_{AW} + \beta\lambda A_{AW} = B_{AW}\lambda - B_{AW}\lambda\omega + D_{AW} - \omega D_{AW} - c\omega E_{AW}$$

$$\lambda(A_{AW}\beta - B_{AW} + B_{AW}\omega) = D_{AW} - \omega D_{AW} - c\omega E_{AW} - A_{AW}$$

we solve for λ

$$\lambda = \frac{D_{AW} - \omega D_{AW} - c\omega E_{AW} - A_{AW}}{A_{AW}\beta - B_{AW} + B_{AW}\omega} := \lambda_{\leq}^+. \quad (97)$$

We resubstitute and get

$$\lambda_{\leq}^+ = \frac{g_{\leq}}{f_{\leq}}$$

with

$$f_{\leq} = (1 - c)^2 \left(\frac{\beta}{4(1 + \beta)} - \frac{(1 - \omega)z}{2} \right) \quad (98)$$

(AW.A.17)

$$g_{\leq} = (1 - c)^2 \left((1 - z)(1 - \omega)g_{1\lambda} - \frac{1}{4(1 + \beta)} \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + (1 - z)g_{2\lambda}) \right).$$

In this case $\lambda_{\leq}^+(\omega)$ is considered a function depending on ω (and $\beta, c, \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}, z$) rather than a calculated threshold value λ_{\leq}^+ (for a specific ω). In particular, the algebraic sign of $\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^+(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right|_{\lambda_{\leq}^+}$ helps to determine the dominant policy. From an interpretative point of view, the threshold λ_{\leq}^+ refers to the amount of consumers' generosity, $\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^+(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right|_{\lambda_{\leq}^+}$ to its (local) dependence on consumers' fair-mindedness.

We treat f_{\leq} and g_{\leq} as rational functions of ω .

$$\lambda^+ = \frac{g_{\leq}(\omega)}{f_{\leq}(\omega)}$$

This allows us to use implicit differentiation,

$$f'_{\leq} \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^+}{\partial \omega} \lambda_{\leq}^+ + \lambda_{\leq}^+ f'_{\leq} = g'_{\leq},$$

which gives us

$$\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^+(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right|_{\lambda_{\leq}^+} = \frac{f_{\leq} g'_{\leq} - g_{\leq} f'_{\leq}}{f_{\leq}^2}. \quad (99)$$

(AW.A.18)

Which in turn is the derivation of λ with respect to ω at a specific value of λ_{\leq}^+ .

5.5.3 Comparing PAYW-MP to PAYW-SP

We only need to compare large λ ($\lambda > 1/(2 + \beta)$), as PAYW-MP is otherwise dominated by PAAP.

We compare PAYW-MP (54) to PAYW-SP (84) and solve for λ .

Again, we need to collect terms to facilitate computation, this results in

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW-MP,2}^* &= \frac{(1-c)^2\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda(2+\beta) + 2\omega(1-\lambda) - 1}{(2+\beta(1+\omega))\lambda - 1 + \omega} \right) \\ &= \frac{G_{AW}\lambda^2 F_{AW} - 2\omega\lambda^2 F_{AW} - 2\omega\lambda F_{AW} - \lambda F_{AW}}{2(G_{AW}\lambda + \beta\omega\lambda + \omega - 1)}\end{aligned}$$

With $F_{AW} = (1-c)$, $G_{AW} = 2 + \beta$.

for PAYW-MP and

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{PAYW-SP}^* &= (1-\omega)(1-c)^2 \left(\frac{\lambda z}{2} + g_{1\lambda}(1-z) \right) - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + g_{2\lambda}(1-z)) \right) \\ &= H_{AW}\lambda + I_{AW}\end{aligned}$$

with $H_{AW} = \frac{(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 z}{2}$, $I_{AW} = (1-\omega)(1-c)^2(1-z)g_{1\lambda} - c\omega \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + (1-z)g_{2\lambda}) \right)$ for PAYW-SP.

We set the two functions equal to each other,

$$\frac{G_{AW}\lambda^2 F_{AW} - 2\omega\lambda^2 F_{AW} - 2\omega\lambda F_{AW} - \lambda F_{AW}}{2(G_{AW}\lambda + \beta\omega\lambda + \omega - 1)} = H_{AW}\lambda + I_{AW}$$

and collect the λ -terms

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{2}G_{AW}\lambda^2 F_{AW} - \omega\lambda^2 F_{AW} - \omega\lambda F_{AW} - \frac{1}{2}\lambda F_{AW} &= (H_{AW}\lambda + I_{AW})(G_{AW}\lambda + \beta\omega\lambda + \omega - 1) \\ \left(\frac{F_{AW}G_{AW}}{2} - F_{AW}\omega - H_{AW}G_{AW} - H_{AW}\beta\omega \right) \lambda^2 & \\ + \left(H_{AW} - I_{AW}G_{AW} - \beta\omega I_{AW} - \omega F_{AW} - \frac{1}{2}F_{AW} - H_{AW}\omega \right) \lambda &+ I_{AW} - \omega I_{AW} \\ &= 0.\end{aligned}$$

We solve the quadratic equation

$$\lambda = \frac{-g_{>} \pm \sqrt{g_{>}^2 - 4f_{>}j_{>}}{2f_{>}} := \lambda_{> 1,2}^+ \quad (100)$$

with

(AW.A.19)

$$f_{>} = H_{AW} - I_{AW}G_{AW} - \beta\omega I_{AW} - \omega F_{AW} - \frac{1}{2}F_{AW} - H_{AW}\omega$$

$$j_{>} = (1 - \omega)I_{AW}.$$

Finally, we resubstitute. This results in

$$\lambda_{>}^{+}{}_{1,2} = \frac{-g_{>} \pm \sqrt{g_{>}^2 - 4f_{>}j_{>}}{2f_{>}}$$

with

$$f_{>} = (1 - c)^2 \left(\frac{z\beta\omega^2}{2} + (1 - z) \left(\frac{2 + \beta}{2} - \omega \right) \right) \quad (101)$$

$$g_{>} = (1 - c)^2 \left(\omega^2 \left(\frac{z}{2} + \beta(1 - z)g_{1\lambda} \right) - (1 - z) \left(\frac{1}{2} + (2 + \beta - 2\omega)g_{1\lambda} \right) \right. \\ \left. - (1 + z)\omega \right) + c\omega(2 + \beta + \beta\omega) \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + g_{2\lambda}(1 - z)) \right) \quad (A.19)$$

$$j_{>} = (1 - c)^2(1 - \omega)^2(1 - z)g_{1\lambda} \\ - c\omega(1 - \omega) \left(1 - \bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}(cz + (1 - z)g_{2\lambda}) \right).$$

Thus, we can collect the optimal pricing choice as in Proposition 4:

Updated Proposition 4. PAYW is never the preferred pricing policy.

- (i) Low levels of generosity $\left(0 \leq \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2+\beta} \right)$:
 - if $\lambda_{\leq}^{+} < 0$ then PAAP is optimal;
 - if $\lambda_{\leq}^{+} \in \left[0; \frac{1}{2+\beta} \right]$ and $\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^{+}(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right|_{\lambda_{\leq}^{+}} > 0$ PAAP is optimal for $\lambda < \lambda_{\leq}^{+}$ but PAYW-SP for $\lambda > \lambda_{\leq}^{+}$;
 - if $\lambda_{\leq}^{+} \in \left[0; \frac{1}{2+\beta} \right]$ and $\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^{+}(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right|_{\lambda_{\leq}^{+}} < 0$ PAYW-SP is optimal;
 - if $\lambda_{\leq}^{+} > \frac{1}{2+\beta}$ PAAP is optimal for $\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^{+}(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right|_{\lambda_{\leq}^{+}} > 0$ but PAYW-SP for $\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^{+}(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right|_{\lambda_{\leq}^{+}} < 0$.
- (ii) Intermediate levels of generosity $\left(\frac{1}{2+\beta} < \lambda \leq \frac{2(1+B_S)}{3} \right)$:
 - if $\lambda \in \left[\frac{1}{2+\beta}; \lambda_{>}^{+} \right]$ then PAYW-SP is optimal;
 - if $\lambda \notin \left[\frac{1}{2+\beta}; \lambda_{>}^{+} \right]$ then PAYW-MP is optimal.
- (iii) High levels of generosity $\left(\frac{2(1+B_S)}{3} < \lambda \leq 1 \right)$: PAYW-MP is optimal.

For an interpretation of these results please cf. to Akbari and Wagner (2020).

6 Simulation analysis

We run a simulation analysis in our submitted manuscript. The procedure was as follows,

- 1) Simulate the data for different points of the parameter space,
- 2) estimate the effect of the misspecifications of CKZ.

To allow reproducibility, the code for data generation and analysis follows as part of this section.

6.1 Data generation

The data was generated in Mathematica 11.0. The following code generates an Excel spreadsheet with profit calculations for all combinations of $\omega \in \{0, .25, .50, 0.75\}$, $\lambda \in \{0, .25, .5, 0.75, 1\}$, $\beta \in \{0, 1.5, 4, 6.5, 9\}$, $c \in \{0, .25, .5, .75\}$, $\tilde{\gamma}_{[0,1]} \in \{0, .25, .5, .75\}$, and $z \in \{0, .25, 0.5, .75\}$ for all pricing schemes, and for our profit functions (6), (17), (54), and (84) and the adapted profit functions by CKZ (7), (19), (43), (61), (63), (95), and (96).

The profits following our profit functions are calculated by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{PAAP}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] &:= \frac{(1-c)^2 (1+\beta \lambda)}{4 (1+\beta)} \\
 \text{AWPAYW}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] &:= (\lambda (1-\omega) (1-c)^2) / 2 - c \omega (1-c \gamma) \\
 \text{AWPAYWMP}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] &:= \begin{cases} \frac{(1-c)^2 (1-\lambda) \lambda}{1+\beta \lambda} & \lambda \leq 1 / (2 + \beta) \\ \frac{(1-c)^2 \lambda (-1+(2+\beta) \lambda+2 (1-\lambda) \omega)}{2 (-1+\omega+\lambda (2+\beta (1+\omega)))} & \lambda > 1 / (2 + \beta) \\ \emptyset & \text{True} \end{cases} \\
 \text{AWPAYWSP}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] &:= \begin{cases} \left((1-c)^2 \left(\frac{1-z}{4} + \frac{z \lambda}{2} \right) (1-\omega) - c \left(1 - (1-z+c z) \gamma \right) \omega \right) & \frac{c \gamma \omega}{(1-c) (1-\omega)} > \frac{1}{2} \\ \left((1-c)^2 (1-\omega) \left(\frac{z \lambda}{2} + \frac{1}{3} (1-z) \left(1 - \frac{c^2 \gamma^2 \omega^2}{(1-c)^2 (1-\omega)^2} \right) \right) - \right. & \frac{c \gamma \omega}{(1-c) (1-\omega)} \leq \frac{1}{2} \ \&\& \ \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{c \gamma \omega}{(1-c) (1-\omega)} \right) \\ \left. c \omega \left(1 - \gamma \left(c z + \frac{1}{3} (1-z) \left(2 + c + \frac{2 c \gamma \omega}{1-\omega} \right) \right) \right) \right) & \\ \left((1-c)^2 (1-\omega) \left(\frac{z \lambda}{2} + (1-z) \lambda \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{c^2 \gamma^2 \omega^2}{(1-c)^2 (-2+3 \lambda) (1-\omega)^2} \right) \right) - \right. & \frac{c \gamma \omega}{(1-c) (1-\omega)} \leq \frac{1}{2} \ \&\& \ \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \left(1 + \frac{c \gamma \omega}{(1-c) (1-\omega)} \right) \\ \left. c \omega \left(1 - \gamma \left(c z + (1-z) \left(c + \frac{2 c \gamma \lambda \omega}{(-2+3 \lambda) (1-\omega)} \right) \right) \right) \right) & \\ \emptyset & \text{True} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

The profits with the prices derived by CKZ in the correct profit functions are calculated by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{CKZPAYWMPinAW}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] = \\
& -\frac{1}{2\lambda(1+\beta\lambda)} \left(\lambda^2(1+\beta\lambda)(-1+\omega) - 2c\lambda(1+\beta\lambda)(-\lambda + (-1+\lambda)\omega) + \right. \\
& \quad \left. c^2(-1+\lambda)(1-\lambda(1+\beta+\beta\lambda)) - \omega + (1+\beta(-1+\lambda))\lambda\omega \right) + \\
& \quad 2(c - c(2+\beta)\lambda + (c(-1+\lambda) - \lambda)(1+\beta\lambda)\omega) \underset{\substack{\text{größte} \cdots \\ \text{kleinstes Element}}}{\text{Max}[c, \text{Min}[c+\lambda - c\lambda, c - \frac{(-1+c)\lambda\omega}{-1+2\lambda+\omega}]]} + \\
& \quad \left(-1+\omega+\lambda(2+\beta+\beta\omega) \right) \text{Max}[c, \text{Min}[c+\lambda - c\lambda, c - \frac{(-1+c)\lambda\omega}{-1+2\lambda+\omega}]]^2) \\
& \text{CKZPAYWSPinAW}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] = \\
& \left[\begin{array}{l} \left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{3}(-2-c) \right) (-c + \frac{2+c}{3}) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{c^2}{2} - \frac{1}{3}c(2+c) + \frac{1}{18}(2+c)^2 \right) \right) (1-z)(1-\omega) + \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \\ z \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} - c\lambda + \frac{c^2\lambda}{2} \right) (1-\omega) - c(z(1-c\gamma)\omega + (1-z)(1 - \frac{1}{3}(2+c)\gamma)\omega) \\ \frac{1}{2}(-(-1+c)^2\lambda(-1+\omega) + 2c(-1+c\gamma)\omega) \quad \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \\ \emptyset \quad \text{True} \end{array} \right.
\end{aligned}$$

The profits with CKZs profit functions are calculated by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{CKZPAYW}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] = (\lambda(1-\omega)(1-c)^2) / (2) - c\omega \\
& \text{CKZPAYWMP}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] = ((1-c)^2\lambda(1-2\omega(1-\lambda) - 2\lambda)) / (2(1-\omega - 2\lambda)) \\
& \text{CKZPAYWSP}[\beta_-, \omega_-, \lambda_-, c_-, \gamma_-, z_-] = \left[\begin{array}{l} -c\omega + ((2+z(3\lambda-2))(1-c)^2(1-\omega)) / 6 \quad \lambda \leq \frac{2}{3} \\ (\lambda/2)(1-\omega)(1-c)^2 - c\omega \quad \lambda > \frac{2}{3} \\ \emptyset \quad \text{True} \end{array} \right.
\end{aligned}$$

Data generation will be performed as follows:

```

fObs = Flatten[Table[{
  |ebne ein |Tabelle
  PAAP[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  AWPAYW[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  AWPAYWMP[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  AWPAYWSP[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  CKZPAYWMPinAW[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  CKZPAYWSPinAW[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  CKZPAYW[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  CKZPAYWMP[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  CKZPAYWSP[β, ω, λ, c, γ, z],
  β,
  ω,
  λ,
  c,
  γ,
  z}, {ω, {0, .25, .50, 0.75}},
{λ, {0.0001, .250001, .500001, 0.750001, 1}}, {β, {9, 6.5, 4, 1.5, 0}},
{c, {0, .25, .5, .75}}, {γ, {0, .25, .5, .75}}, {z, {0, .25, 0.5, .75}}, 5];

```

Finally, we export the data to an excel spreadsheet.

```
Export[NotebookDirectory[] <> "profits_AW_CKZaw_CKZ.xls",
exporti... [Notebook-Verzeichnis
Map[NumberForm[N@#, {4, 3}] &, fObs, {2}]]
lw... [Zahlenform [numerischer Wert
```

6.2 Data analysis

Data analysis was performed in R 3.6.2. In short, we load the previously generated data and measure forecast accuracy using different approaches. The final manuscript only makes use of the MAAPE and iMAPE.

6.2.1 Setup

First, the necessary data and R packages are loaded.

```
library(dplyr)
library(readxl)
library(tidyverse)
library(knitr)
library(kableExtra)
library(xtable)
```

Second, the data is loaded, and the variables are renamed.

```
path <- "\\FILEPATH\\profits_AW_CKZaw_CKZ.xls"

profits <- read_excel(path,
                      col_names = FALSE)

profits <- profits %>%
  rename(PAAP = X__1,
         AWPAYW = X__2,
         AWPAYWMP = X__3,
         AWPAYWSP = X__4,
         CKZinAWPAYWMP = X__5,
         CKZinAWPAYWSP = X__6,
         CKZPAYW = X__7,
         CKZPAYWMP = X__8,
         CKZPAYWSP = X__9,
         beta = X__10,
         omega = X__11,
         lambda = X__12,
```

```

c = X__13,
gamma = X__14,
z = X__15)

```

6.2.2 Measuring the forecast error

Next, different alternatives for measuring forecast accuracy are defined.

```

imatepe <- function(a, f) {
  data <- data.frame(a, f) %>%
    filter(a != 0)
  data$e <- data$a - data$f
  data$p <- data$e / data$a
  mape <- mean(abs(data$p))
  mape
}

maape <- function(a, f){
  aape <- atan(abs((a - f) / a))
  maape <- mean(aape)
  maape
}

smape <- function(a, f){
  ape <- abs((a - f) / ((a + f) / 2))
  smape <- mean(ape)
  smape
}

madmean <- function(a, f){
  ad <- abs(a - f)
  mad <- mean(ad)
  madmean <- mad / (mean(a))
  madmean
}

smdape <- function(a, f){
  ape <- abs((a - f) / ((a + f) / 2))
  smdape <- median(ape)
  smdape
}

```

```
}

```

6.2.3 Calculation of differences and relative differences

Differences between the profits after CKZ and the correct formulation are calculated.

```
#----- Calculation of differences ----- #
profits_diff <- profits %>%
  mutate(PAYWDiff = AWPAYW - CKZPAYW,
         PAYWMPDiffinAW = AWPAYWMP - CKZinAWPAYWMP,
         PAYWSPDiffinAW = AWPAYWSP - CKZinAWPAYWSP,
         PAYWMPDiffPiCKZ = AWPAYWMP - CKZPAYWMP,
         PAYWSPDiffPiCKZ = AWPAYWSP - CKZPAYWSP
        ) %>%
  mutate(PAYWRelDiff = PAYWDiff/(CKZPAYW),
         PAYWMPRelDiffinAW = PAYWMPDiffinAW/CKZinAWPAYWMP,
         PAYWSPRelDiffinAW =PAYWSPDiffinAW/CKZinAWPAYWSP,
         PAYWMPRelDiff = PAYWMPDiffPiCKZ/CKZPAYWMP ,
         PAYWSPRelDiff = PAYWSPDiffPiCKZ/CKZPAYWSP)

```

6.2.4 Calculation of optimal choices

In this step, the calculation of optimal choices for the seller is performed for both of CKZ's specifications and the correct specification by finding the maximum profit for each scenario.

```
profits_aw <- tibble(PAAP = profits_diff$PAAP,
                   PAYWMP = profits_diff$AWPAYWMP,
                   PAYWSP = profits_diff$AWPAYWSP)

profits_CKZ_inAW <- tibble(PAAP = profits_diff$PAAP,
                          PAYWMP = profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWMP,
                          PAYWSP = profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWSP)

profits_CKZ_own_function <- tibble(PAAP = profits_diff$PAAP,
                                   PAYWMP = profits_diff$CKZPAYWMP,
                                   PAYWSP = profits_diff$CKZPAYWSP)

AW_choice <- colnames(profits_aw)[apply(profits_aw,1,which.max)]
CKZ_inAW_choice <- colnames(profits_CKZ_inAW)[apply(profits_CKZ_inAW,1,which.max)]
CKZ_own_function_choice <- colnames(profits_CKZ_own_function)[apply(profits_CKZ_own_function,1,which.max)]

```

This gives us the following interim results. Following the correct specification, we find the that seller decides in favor of pricing schemes as follows:

```
table(AW_choice) %>%
  kable() %>%
  kable_styling()
```

AW_choice	Freq
PAAP	1212
PAYWMP	3805
PAYWSP	1383

Using CKZ's prices in correct profit function would yield the following optimal pricing decisions:

```
table(CKZ_inAW_choice) %>%
  kable() %>%
  kable_styling()
```

CKZ_inAW_choice	Freq
PAAP	2238
PAYWMP	2782
PAYWSP	1380

Using CKZ's initial profit functions would yield the following decisions:

```
table(CKZ_own_function_choice) %>%
  kable() %>%
  kable_styling()
```

CKZ_own_function_choice	Freq
PAAP	1104
PAYWMP	4160

CKZ_own_function_choice**Freq**

PAYWSP

1136

The following tables show differences between the different models:

```
disagreement_inAW <- table(CKZ_inAW_choice, AW_choice)
disagreement_inAW %>%
  kable() %>%
  add_header_above(c("CKZ in AW", "AW"=3)) %>%
  kable_styling()
```

	CKZ in AW		AW	
	PAAP	PAYWMP	PAYWSP	
PAAP	1212	1026	0	
PAYWMP	0	2686	96	
PAYWSP	0	93	1287	

6.2.5 Calculation of forecast error

Now we can define the forecast error for the different setups:

6.2.5.1 CKZ in our profit functions

```
tabelle <- cbind(
  c(
    imape(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW),
    maape(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW),
    smape(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW),
    madmean(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW)
  ),
  c(imape(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWMP),
    maape(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWMP),
    smape(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWMP),
    madmean(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWMP)
  ),
)
```

```

c(imape(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWSP),
  maape(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWSP),
  smape(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWSP),
  madmean(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZinAWPAYWSP)
))

colnames(tabelle) <- c("PAYW", "PAYW-MP", "PAYW-SP")
rownames(tabelle) <- c("iMAPE", "MAAPE", "sMAPE", "MAD/Mean")

kable(tabelle, digits = 2)%>%
  kable_styling()

```

	PAYW	PAYW-MP	PAYW-SP
iMAPE	0.29	0.24	0.10
MAAPE	0.19	0.21	0.07
sMAPE	0.20	0.35	0.11
MAD/Mean	-0.84	0.08	-1.95

6.2.5.2 CKZ's profit functions

```

tabelle <- cbind(
  c(
    imape(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW),
    maape(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW),
    smape(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW),
    madmean(profits_diff$AWPAYW, profits_diff$CKZPAYW)
  ),
  c(imape(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWMP),
    maape(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWMP),
    smape(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWMP),
    madmean(profits_diff$AWPAYWMP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWMP)
  ),
  c(imape(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWSP),
    maape(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWSP),

```

```

    smape(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWSP),
    madmean(profits_diff$AWPAYWSP, profits_diff$CKZPAYWSP)
  ))

colnames(tabelle) <- c("PAYW", "PAYW-MP", "PAYW-SP")
rownames(tabelle) <- c("iMAPE", "MAAPE", "sMAPE", "MAD/Mean")

kable(tabelle, digits = 2) %>%
  kable_styling()

```

	PAYW	PAYW-MP	PAYW-SP
iMAPE	0.29	6792.04	0.72
MAAPE	0.19	0.36	0.29
sMAPE	0.20	149.04	0.47
MAD/Mean	-0.84	3866.55	-14.93

References

- Akbari K, Wagner U (2020) Comments and Refinements on the Pay as you wish Model by Chen et al. (2017).
- Chen Y, Koenigsberg O, Zhang ZJ (2017) Pay-as-You-Wish Pricing. *Marketing Science*. 36(5):780–791.

List of Symbols

The following symbols are a collection and comparison of symbols in Akbari and Wagner (2020), CKZ and this report. The symbols are listed in order of appearance.

Section 2: PWYW and critical costs

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
i		i	Index of individual consumer
u_i		u_i	Consumer i 's utility
r_i		r_i	Consumer i 's consumption utility
p_i		p_i	Consumer i 's price
β_i		β_i	Consumer i 's disadvantageous inequity aversion parameter
γ_i		γ_i	Consumer i 's advantageous inequity aversion parameter
r_{i0}		r_{i0}	Consumer i 's perceived fair price
c		c	Firm's costs
λ		λ	Generosity
p_h		p_h	Highest possible fair price
p_{PAAP}^*		p_{PAAP}^*	Optimal price in PAAP
$PAAP$		$PAAP$	Pay as asked pricing
AW		AW	Akbari and Wagner (2020)
		$u_{\tilde{r}}$	Marginal consumer's utility
		\tilde{r}	Consumption utility for the marginal consumer with advantageous inequity aversion
		p_{PAAP}	Price in PAAP
		\tilde{r}^+	Critical consumption utility of the marginal consumer
		β	Disadvantageous inequity aversion parameter
		r^+	Consumption utility marginal consumer with disadvantageous inequity
		π_{PAAP}	Profits under PAAP
		π_{PAAP}^*	Optimal profits under PAAP
		$\pi_{PAAP}^{\beta=0,*}$	Optimal profits under PAAP with $\beta = 0$

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
<i>Segment I</i> _{PAYW} ^a			Freeloader segment in PAYW (high consumption utility)
<i>Segment I</i> _{PAYW} ^b			Freeloader segment in PAYW (low consumption utility)
<i>Segment II</i> _{PAYW}			Non-buyer segment in PAYW (less fair-minded consumers)
<i>Segment III</i> _{PAYW}			Paying customers segment in PAYW
<i>Segment IV</i> _{PAYW}			Non-buyer segment in PAYW (more fair-minded consumers)
$\phi(r)$		$\phi(r)$	Density function of consumption utilities
$h(\gamma)$		$h(\gamma)$	Density function of advantageous inequity aversion
θ^{CKZ}		θ^{CKZ}	CKZ's share of freeloaders
θ		θ_{PAYW}	Share of freeloaders
δ		δ_{PAYW}	Share of less fair-minded consumers who remain non-buyers in PAYW
π_{PAYW}		π_{PAYW}^*	Profits under PAYW
π_{PAYW}^{CKZ}		$\pi_{PAYW}^{*,CKZ}$	Profits under PAYW in CKZ
$\Delta \pi$		$\Delta \pi$	Profit difference in PAYW between AW and CKZ
ω		ω	Less fair-minded consumers
$(1 - \omega)$		$(1 - \omega)$	More fair-minded consumers
$\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$		$\bar{\gamma}_{[0,1]}$	Mean of γ_i in $[0,1]$
$h_{[0,1]}$		$h_{[0,1]}$	Distribution of γ_i in $[0,1]$
c^+		c^+	Critical cost level above which PAYW cannot be profitable
A		A_{COMP}	Auxiliary variable in c^+
B		B_{COMP}	Auxiliary variable in c^+
		p_i^*	Consumers optimal price in PAYW
		D_{COMP}	Auxiliary variable in c^+
		E_{COMP}	Auxiliary variable in c^+
		ω^+	Critical threshold of freeloaders
		A_{COMP}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in c^+ for CKZ
		B_{COMP}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in c^+ for CKZ
		D_{COMP}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in c^+ for CKZ
	c^*	$c^{CKZ,+}$	Critical threshold of costs for PAYW to dominate PAAP

Section 3: Minimum price

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
\underline{p}		\underline{p}	Minimum price
$PAYW-MP$		MP	PAYW with a minimum price
r^+		r^+	Critical consumption utility that a consumer buys in PAYW-MP
p_f		p_f	Perceived fair price when $r_i > c$
\underline{p}^u		\underline{p}^u	Consumption utility at the minimum price
\underline{r}		\underline{r}	Critical consumption utility for which minimum price equal fair price
Segment $I_{PAYW-MP}^a$			Freeloader segment in PAYW-MP (suffering from advantageous inequity)
Segment $I_{PAYW-MP}^b$			Freeloader segment in PAYW-MP (suffering from disadvantageous inequity)
Segment $II_{PAYW-MP}^a$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-MP because of disadvantageous inequity aversion (less fair-minded consumers)
Segment $II_{PAYW-MP}^b$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-MP because of low consumption utility (less fair-minded consumers)
Segment $III_{PAYW-MP}^a$			Paying customers segment in PAYW-MP (fair price)
Segment $III_{PAYW-MP}^b$			Paying customers segment in PAYW-MP (minimum price)
Segment $IV_{PAYW-MP}^a$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-MP because of disadvantageous inequity aversion (more fair-minded consumers)
Segment $IV_{PAYW-MP}^b$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-MP because of low consumption utility (more fair-minded consumers)
$\pi_{PAYW-MP}$		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}$	Profits under PAYW-MP
\underline{p}^*		\underline{p}^*	Optimal minimum price
$\underline{p}^{CKZ,*}$		$\underline{p}^{CKZ,*}$	Optimal minimum price in CKZ
	k	G_{MP}	Auxiliary variable distinguishing the optimal minimum price for high/low values of generosity, λ
	a		Auxiliary variable for minimum price
	b		Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^*$	Optimal profits under PAYW-MP
		$A_{MP}^{\beta=0}$	Auxiliary variable for minimum price when $\beta = 0$

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0}$	Profits in PWYW-MP with no disadvantageous inequity aversion
		$B_{MP}^{\beta=0}$	Auxiliary variable for minimum price when $\beta=0$
		$D_{MP}^{\beta=0}$	Auxiliary variable for minimum price when $\beta=0$
		p_h	Highest possible fair price
		$E_{MP}^{\beta=0}$	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\beta=0,*}$	Profits in PWYW-MP for CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZ}$	
		$p^{\beta=0,*}$	Optimal minimum price in PWYW-MP for CKZ
		$\bar{p}^{CKZ,*}$	
		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{\bar{CKZ},*}$	Optimal profits in PWYW-MP for CKZ
		A_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		B_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		D_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		E_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		F_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		G_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^*$	Optimal profits in PWYW-MP
		H_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		I_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		J_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		K_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		L_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price
		M_{MP}	Auxiliary variable for minimum price

Section 4: Suggested price

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
$PAYW-SP$		s	PAYW with a suggested price
p_s		p_s	Suggested price
$(1 - z)$		$(1 - z)$	Probability that consumers pay attention to the suggested price
z		z	Probability that consumers ignore the suggested price
r_s		r_s	Critical consumption utility for which suggested price equal fair price
Segment $I_{PAYW-SP}^a$			Freeloader segment in PAYW-SP (very high consumption utility)
Segment $I_{PAYW-SP}^b$			Freeloader segment in PAYW-SP (high consumption utility)
Segment $I_{PAYW-SP}^c$			Freeloader segment in PAYW-SP (low consumption utility)
Segment $I_{PAYW-SP}^d$			Freeloader segment in PAYW-SP (very low consumption utility)
Segment $II_{PAYW-SP}^a$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-SP with high consumption utility (less fair-minded consumers)
Segment $II_{PAYW-SP}^b$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-SP with low consumption utility (less fair-minded consumers)
Segment $III_{PAYW-SP}^a$			Paying customers segment in PAYW-SP (fair price)
Segment $III_{PAYW-SP}^b$			Paying customers segment in PAYW-SP (suggested price)
Segment $III_{PAYW-SP}^c$			Paying customers segment in PAYW-SP (paying consumption utility)
Segment $IV_{PAYW-SP}^a$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-SP with high consumption utility (more fair-minded consumers)
Segment $IV_{PAYW-SP}^b$			Non-buyer segment in PAYW-SP with low consumption utility (more fair-minded consumers)
θ_s^z		θ_s^z	Share of freeloaders that ignore price suggestion in PAYW-SP
θ_s^{1-z}		θ_s^{1-z}	Share of freeloaders that consider price suggestion in PAYW-SP
δ_s^z		δ_s^z	Share of less fair-minded consumers who remain non-buyers in PAYW-SP and ignore the price suggestion
δ_s^{1-z}		δ_s^{1-z}	Share of less fair-minded consumers who remain non-buyers in PAYW-SP and consider the price suggestion
$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^1$		$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^1$	Profits under PAYW-SP when suggested price is low
$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^2$		$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^2$	Firm's profits under PAYW-SP when suggested price is high
p_s^*		p_s^*	Optimal suggested price

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
m		B_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP, threshold that determines whether costs, the share of fair-minded consumers and their fair-mindedness is high
$g_{1\lambda}$		$g_{1\lambda}$	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP
$g_{2\lambda}$		$g_{2\lambda}$	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP
		$p_{f,s}$	Fair price in the presence of a suggested price
		p_s^u	Utility at the suggested price
		$p_{f,s}, c < r \leq p_s^u$	Fair price for high consumption utilities
		$p_{s,1}^{CKZ*}$	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ}$	Profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price in CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{CKZ*}$	Optimal profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price in CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ}$	Profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price in CKZ
		$p_{s,2}^{CKZ*}$	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{CKZ*}$	Optimal profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price in CKZ
		p_s^{CKZ*}	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}$	Profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,1}^{z=0}$	Profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price
		$p_{s,1a}^*$	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		$p_{s,1b}^*$	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		A_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP
		$p_{s,1}^*$	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		D_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}$	Profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP,2}^{z=0}$	Profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price
		$p_{s,2a}^*$	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		$p_{s,2b}^*$	Optimal suggested price in CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^*$	Optimal profits under PAYW-SP with suggested price
		E_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP
		F_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
		G_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP
		H_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP
		$\bar{V}_{[0,1]}^{\min}$	Minimum feasible $\bar{V}_{[0,1]}$
		$\bar{V}_{[0,1]}^{\max}$	Maximum feasible $\bar{V}_{[0,1]}$
		I_s	Auxiliary variable in PAYW-SP

Section 5: Profit comparisons

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
λ^+		λ^+	Threshold that separates regions in which PAYW-SP or other pricing mechanism is optimal
λ_{\leq}^+		λ_{\leq}^+	Threshold that separates regions in which PAYW-SP or PAAP are optimal
$\lambda_{>}^+$		$\lambda_{>}^+$	Threshold that separates regions in which PAYW-SP or PAYW-SP are optimal
$\bar{V}_{[0,1]}^{\min}$		$\bar{V}_{[0,1]}^{\min}$	Minimum feasible $\bar{V}_{[0,1]}$
$\bar{V}_{[0,1]}^{\max}$		$\bar{V}_{[0,1]}^{\max}$	Maximum feasible $\bar{V}_{[0,1]}$
β^{\min}		β^{\min}	Minimum feasible β
β^{\max}		β^{\max}	Maximum feasible β
$\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^+(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right _{\lambda_{\leq}^+}$		$\left. \frac{\partial \lambda_{\leq}^+(\omega)}{\partial \omega} \right _{\lambda_{\leq}^+}$	Amount of consumers' generosity to its local dependence on consumers' fair mindedness
A_i			Actual observations (AW's results)
F_i			Forecast values (CKZ's results)
		θ_{RE}^{CKZ+}	Critical threshold of freeloaders when following CKZ's
		A_{RE}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable for θ_{RE}^{CKZ+}
		B_{RE}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable for θ_{RE}^{CKZ+}
		C_{RE}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable for θ_{RE}^{CKZ+}
		D_{RE}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable for θ_{RE}^{CKZ+}
		$\theta_{RE}^{CKZ,+}$	
		$\theta_{RE}^{CKZ,+} < \lambda < \frac{2}{3}$	Threshold for optimality

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
$\theta^*(z, \lambda, c)$		$\theta_{RE, \lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}}^{CKZ,+}$	Threshold for optimality
		$\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}(z, c, \lambda)$	Threshold for optimality
	A	A_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
	B	B_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
	C	C_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
	D	D_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
	E	E_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
		$\theta_{ORIG}^{CKZ,+}$	Threshold for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
		A_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
		B_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
		D_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
		B_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
		C_{ORIG}^{CKZ}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme in CKZ
		$\pi_{PAYW-MP}^{CKZnew,*}$	Optimal profits in PWYW-MP
		$\pi_{PAYW-SP}^{CKZnew,*}$	Optimal profits in PWYW-SP
		A_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme
		B_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme
		D_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme
		E_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme
	g_{\leq}	g_{\leq}	Auxiliary variable in optimal choice of PAYW-SP vs. PAAP
	f_{\leq}	f_{\leq}	Auxiliary variable in optimal choice of PAYW-SP vs. PAAP
	$g_{>}$	$g_{>}$	Auxiliary variable in optimal choice of PAYW-SP vs. PAYW-MP
	$f_{>}$	$f_{>}$	Auxiliary variable in optimal choice of PAYW-SP vs. PAYW-MP
	$j_{>}$	$j_{>}$	Auxiliary variable in optimal choice of PAYW-SP vs. PAYW-MP
		F_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme
		G_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme
		H_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme
		I_{AW}	Auxiliary variable in determination for optimal choice of pricing scheme

Akbari and Wagner (2020)	CKZ	This Report	Explanation
<i>MAPE</i>			Mean absolute percentage error, Measure of prediction accuracy of a forecasting method
<i>iMAPE</i>			Mean absolute percentage error excluding 0 actual profits, Measure of prediction accuracy of a forecasting method
<i>MAAPE</i>			Mean arctangent absolute percentage error
